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Ministry of Higher Education
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Middle Technical University
College of Health and Medical Technology/Baghdad

**Detection of Potential β -cell Stress and/or Death Biomarkers
in Patients with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus in Thi-Qar
Province**

A THESIS SUBMITTED TO
THE COLLEGE COUNCIL OF HEALTH AND MEDICAL
TECHNOLOGY AS A PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF DOCTORATE OF
TECHNOLOGY IN PHILOSOPHY OF MEDICAL
LABORATORY SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY

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بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

«وَلِكُلِّ دَرَجَةٍ مِمَّا عَمِلُوا وَمَا رَبُّكَ بِغَفِلٍ عَمَّا يَعْمَلُونَ»

صدق الله العلي العظيم

سُورَةُ الْأَنْعَامِ/الآيَةُ ١٣٢

Dedication

To the owner of the greatest honor, the venerable prophet, our prophet Mohammed the messenger of Allah (Allah pray and peace upon him and his family), and I request his intercession in the doomsday, to his chaste sinless household, and his kind companions.

To the scion of prophecy house, the lion-hearted imam, the owner of the epoch and this time, to the all religious leaders and good righteous people.

To ... my father ... (mercy of Allah on him and made the paradise his home).

To ... my mother/aunt ... who I am shading in her appeal, I ask long life for her, and giving her the best of what he gave to mother from her son.

To ... the piece of my eye, my wife.

To ... the sources of science and knowledge, my professors.

To ... the origin of loyalty my brothers.

To ... all who helped me in my humble research.

To them I dedicate what accommodate darling Allah sincerely and gratitude.

Hasan Abd Ali Khudhair

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Finally, to whomever I have forgotten to mention their names I dedicate my thanks and my gratitude.

Hasan Abd Ali Khudhair

Summary

Diabetes Mellitus type 1 (T1D) occurs due to disturbance in the tolerance of immune system and invasion of beta (β)-cells by auto-reactive immune T cells, and induction of loss of β -cells function and mass, resulting in prolonged therapy with exogenous insulin. One of the biggest therapeutic challenges which are in most occasions turns the disease into only partially treatable but not curable is the bad condition of the pancreas at diagnosis. The disease T1D has long prodromal or preclinical stages that may last for years and during which the majority of the pancreatic islets of Langerhans β -cells (about 90%) were destroyed. Accordingly, at the time of diagnosis during the clinical stage, indeed a very few number of the insulin producing β -cells were left which guides the treatment towards hormonal replacement therapy. Many studies and trials have tested several methods to stop β -cells deterioration and/or to predict that through certain indicators or biomarkers but unfortunately with no use.

This study was aimed to detect the predictive power and the degree of correlation of defined classical T1D semi-specific biomarkers (glutamic acid decarboxylase autoantibody (GADA) and islets antigen-2 autoantibody (IA-2A)), T1D-nonspecific biomarker such as (total antioxidant capacity (TAC)) and non-classical undefined biomarkers (micro-ribonucleic acid (miRNA)-25 and miRNA-375) on β -cells stress and/or death in T1D patients and their first degree relatives (FDRs). Thirty five T1D patients (17 males and 18 females) and thirty five individuals of their FDRs (22 males and 13 females) attending the Diabetes and Endocrinology Specialist Center at Thi-Qar province during the period between May 2018 and November 2018, with age range of 10-18 years and 4-39 years, respectively, and twenty apparently healthy

individuals (10 males and 10 females) with age range of 5-30 years were enrolled in this study and evaluated for their serum GADA, IA-2A, connecting (C) peptide, TAC and expression levels of miRNA-25 and miRNA-375. The results revealed positive GADA and IA-2A in 88.6% and 40%, respectively, of T1D patients. The frequency of above normal level and mean titer of C-peptide were significantly low among T1D patients and their FDRs, also the frequency of normal level and mean titer of TAC was significantly low among T1D patients. Concerning miRNAs expression, the frequencies of high level and/or high mean titer of miRNA-25 were significantly low in T1D and their FDRs with diagnostic sensitivity of 94.7% and specificity of 100%. Micro-RNA-375 results revealed low level in 35% of T1D patient and in 10% of FDRs, whereas the mean titer was significantly higher among FDRs individuals in comparison to healthy control (HC) subjects. No significant differences for IA-2A positivity, C-peptide level and miRNA-375 expression were noticed between the GADA⁺ and GADA⁻ subjects, whereas miRNA-25 level was significantly lower for GADA⁺ than GADA⁻ individuals of T1D and FDRs and GADA titer was positively correlated with increased miRNA-25 expression in T1D patients. On the other hand, there was an inverse correlation between GADA positivity and TAC serum level. Such correlation was absent between IA-2A positivity and TAC serum level. This means a vital participation of GADA in pancreatic oxidative stress (OS).

The concentrations of C-peptide and miRNA-25 were significantly lower in IA-2A positive than IA-2A negative individuals, whereas the level of miRNA-375 was significantly higher in IA-2A positive than IA-2A negative FDRs subjects. In addition to that, no significant effect of TAC level on IA-2A positivity and concentration of C-peptide. The

miRNA-25 level was significantly lower in subjects with below normal C-peptide than subjects with normal or above normal C-peptide levels, whereas there was a significant elevation in miRNA-375 level among the individuals with below normal C-peptide compared to individuals with normal or above normal level of C-peptide. Furthermore, miRNA-25 level was statistically highest in individuals with low miRNA-375 level than those with high level. Finally, T1D patients and FDRs subjects with below normal TAC level coincides with significantly higher expression level of miRNA-25 and lower expression level of miRNA-375. In conclusion, GADA, IA-2A and C-peptide combination can be suggested as the most powerful and cost-effective diagnostic approach in patients with T1D and their FDRs. In addition, IA-2A in T1D patients and their FDRs sera can predict β -cells death and/or stress, whereas GADA and TAC were found of no effect on the C-peptide level and thus were unreliable as predictor biomarkers for β -cells stress and/or death. Micro-RNA-25 had expressed a decreased level among the new onset T1D patients and their FDRs, whereas miRNA-375 had expressed a decreased level among newly onset T1D and elevated level among FDRs. The correlation between the residual β -cells function/mass and miRNA-25 serum level was positive which indicate the possible utility of its low expression as a β -cells stress and/or death predictive biomarker. On the other hand, the correlation between the residual β -cells function/mass and the miRNA-375 serum level was negative which indicate the possible utility of its high expression as a β -cells stress and/or death predictive biomarker.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviate	Explanation
°C	Centigrade
μl	Microliter
μM	Micromolar
Abs	Antibodies
ABTS	2,2'-azino-bis-3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid
ADA	American Diabetes Association
ADP	Adenosine diphosphate
AGEs	Advanced glycation end products
Ago2	Argonaute-2
Ags	Antigens
anti-GAD	Anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase
APC	Antigen-presenting cell
APECED	Autoimmune polyendocrinopathy-candidiasis-ectodermal dystrophy
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
C	Connecting
cAMP	Cyclic adenosine monophosphate
CD	Cluster of differentiation
cDNA	Complementary DNA
CMV	Cytomegalovirus
CREB	cAMP response element binding protein
C _T	Threshold cycle
CTLA4	Cytotoxic T-lymphocyte-associated protein 4
CTLs	Cytotoxic T lymphocytes
CVB	Coxsackie virus B
CVD	Cardiovascular disease
DCs	Dendritic cells
DKA	Diabetic ketoacidosis
DM	Diabetes mellitus
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
ELISA	Enzyme linked immuno-sorbent assay
EPAC2	Exchange protein directly activated by cAMP 2
EXPO5	Exportin 5

FDRs	First degree relatives
FR	Frequency
GABA	Gamma-aminobutyric acid
GADA	Glutamic acid decarboxylase autoantibody
Hb	Hemoglobin
HC	Healthy control
HLA	Human leukocyte antigen
HMGB-1	High Mobility Group Box 1 proteins
HPA	Hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal
HPLC	High pressure liquid chromatography
HRP	Horseradish peroxidase
HSP	Heat Shock Proteins
IA	Insulin antigen
IA-2	Insulinoma-associated Ag 2
IA-2A	Islets antigen-2 autoantibody
IAA	Insulin autoantibodies
ICA	Islet cell antigen
IFIH1	Interferon induced with helicase C domain 1
IFN	Interferons
Ig	Immunoglobulin
IL	Interleukin
IRF-1	Interferon regulatory factor-1
KDa	Kilo Daltons
KIRs	Killer-cell immunoglobulin-like receptors
m	Month
MHC	Major histocompatibility complex
min	Minute
miRNA	Micro-ribonucleic acid
mM	Millimolar
mRNA	Messenger RNA
mt-Cytb	Mitochondrial cytochrome b
NAD	Nicotinamide-adenine dinucleotide
NADPH	Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate hydrogen
NFW	Nuclease free water
ng	Nanogram

NK	Natural killer
nm	Nanometer
NO	Nitric oxide
NPV	Negative predictive value
OD	Optical density
OS	Oxidative stress
PB	Peripheral blood
PBMCs	Peripheral blood mononuclear cells
PKA	Protein kinase A
Pol	Polymerase
PPV	Positive predictive value
Pre-miRNAs	miRNAs precursors
Pri-miRNAs	Primary miRNAs
PTP	Protein tyrosine phosphatase
RIP1	Receptor-interacting protein 1
RISC	RNA induced silencing complex
RNS	Reactive nitrogen species
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
RPM	Round per minute
RT	Reverse transcriptase
RT-qPCR	Reverse transcriptase quantitative polymerase chain reaction
SD	Standard deviations
SPSS	Statistical package for social sciences
STAT-1	Signal transducer and activator of transcription-1
T1D	Diabetes mellitus type 1
TAC	Total antioxidant capacity
TE	Tris-EDTA
T-effs	Effector T
TGF	Transforming growth factor
Th	T-helper
TMB	Tetra-methyl-benzidine
TNF	Tumor necrosis factor
Treg	T regulatory
Txnip	Thioredoxin-interacting protein
U	Unit

UTRs	Untranslated regions
VEGF	Vascular endothelial growth factor
WHO	World Health Organization
Zeb1	Zinc finger E-box-binding homeobox 1
ZnT8	Zinc transporter 8 protein
β	Beta

Chapter One

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Type 1 diabetes arises from a break in immune tolerance and invasion of auto-reactive T cells that target β -cells, and prompt loss of β -cells function and mass and a lifelong requirement for exogenous insulin (Lehuen *et al.*, 2010). Beta-cells destruction in its majority occur in the prodromal stages of T1D that when the diagnosis of the disease is achieved, it became too late as about 90% of the β -cells were destroyed. To preserve β -cells from destruction, a number of immunomodulatory drugs have been tested including anti-cluster of differentiation (CD) 3, anti-CD20, cytotoxic T-lymphocyte-associated protein 4 (CTLA4)-immunoglobulin (Ig), and others. These immunomodulators have led to only a modest preservation of β -cells function without true remission from T1D (Mirmira *et al.*, 2016).

There are other few selected candidate intrinsic pathways in which certain factors might play a role in the death/stress of the low proliferative and regenerative human β -cells during the prodromal stages and early clinical stage (Atkinson *et al.*, 2011). Of these are; the auto-antibodies (Abs), the oxidative stress, the C-peptide/insulin ratio, the expression of variable levels of miRNAs molecules and many others.

Glutamic acid decarboxylase auto-Abs and IA-2A are now being used as a more specific cytoplasmic assay in the diagnosis of type IA autoimmune mediated pancreatic β -cells destruction (Lebastchi and Herold, 2012). Monitoring such systemic auto-Abs is currently the most reliable biomarkers in the prodromal phase of T1D, since their appearance typically precedes overt T1D onset for years or even decades (Wenzlau and Hutton, 2013). However, the predictive value of these markers on the time occurrence of T1D and the degree of death/stress of pancreatic β -cells may goes at the expense of diagnostic sensitivity, as

they detect only about 30% of prediabetic relatives (Truyen *et al.*, 2005). Therefore, there is a need for additional biological markers of higher sensitivity capable of identifying more prediabetic relatives.

In recent years, data characterizing intrinsic β -cells stress and/or death in T1D suggest that processes such as β -cells calcium dys-homeostasis, mis-folded protein accumulation, OS, and endoplasmic reticulum stress become activated early during the evolution of T1D and act to either initiate immune activation through the formation of neo-antigens (Ags) or serve to augment autoimmune-mediated β -cells death and dysfunction (Marré *et al.*, 2015).

Increasing evidence suggests that oxidative stress plays a role in the pathogenesis of T1D and its complications. In addition, antioxidant mechanisms are diminished in diabetic patients, which may further augment OS (Moussa, 2008). Thus, interventions in the newly defined stages 1–2 of the pre-symptomatic phase of T1D (Insel *et al.*, 2015) offer the promise of more effective preservation of β -cells mass (Butler *et al.*, 2010). In such a paradigm, a valid signature of β -cells stress could serve as a signal to initiate immunomodulatory therapy in the pre-T1D period (Insel *et al.*, 2015).

Connecting-peptide is well known to fulfill an important function in the synthesis of insulin. Connecting peptide was found to be useful as an indicator of β -cells function, and has been used as a surrogate marker for monitoring the course of T1D and T2D and determining the effects of interventions designed to preserve and improve residual β -cells function (Wahren *et al.*, 2012). Connecting peptide levels are good indicators of insulin levels in the blood and pancreatic β -cells function (Shetty *et al.*, 2017). The use of C-peptide has arisen as a means to directly assess

destruction of β -cells by autoimmune attack (Lebastchi and Herold, 2012).

Micro-ribonucleic acid are a class of small noncoding RNAs molecules (mostly) that negatively (in most occasions) regulate gene expression by inducing target messenger RNA (mRNA) cleavage or by inhibiting protein translation. Abnormal miRNA expressions have been described in autoimmune diseases including T1D (Zheng *et al.*, 2017).

In the context of diabetes, an emerging literature suggests that specific miRNAs or groups of miRNAs could serve as biomarkers of disease progression or diabetic complications (Zampetaki *et al.*, 2016). Roggli *et al.*, (2010) performed global microarray profiling of human islets treated with a cocktail of proinflammatory cytokines and demonstrated upregulation in miRNA-21, miRNA-34a, and miRNA-146a. Using a different stress paradigm of T1D, Kim *et al.*, (2016) demonstrated increases in miRNA-34a-5p, miRNA-21-3p, miRNA-155-5p, miRNA-1290, miRNA-663b, and miRNA-10b-3p in human islets infected with Coxsackie virus B5, and bioinformatics analysis identified 57 candidate T1D risk genes predicted to be direct targets of Coxsackie virus B5 responsive miRNAs. These findings suggested a pathogenic role of certain miRNAs in β -cells dysfunction in T1D, but still doesn't address whether these and other miRNAs might serve as circulating biomarkers reflecting β -cells stress. Other studies have identified additional miRNAs associated with T1D, emphasizing the correlation between miRNAs and T1D diagnosis and/or control (Osipova *et al.*, 2014). Notably, whereas some of the miRNAs have been shown to be enriched in human β -cells (e.g., miRNA-21, miRNA-24, miRNA-29a, and miRNA-375) (Bunt *et al.*, 2013), many are not, suggesting that they may not be a reflection of endogenous β -cells stress. Nevertheless, miRNAs represent a potentially

promising class of circulating nucleic acids that could serve as biomarkers of individuals at high-risk for T1D, and future studies in high-risk populations are warranted.

1.2 Aim of the Study

To investigate the predictive power and the degree of correlation of defined immunological (GADA and IA-2A), biochemical (TAC) and genetic (miRNA-25 and miRNA-375) biomarkers on β -cells stress and/or death (as represented by C-peptide serum level) in newly diagnosed T1D and their 1st degree relatives. Such predictive power and degree of correlation presumably might provide new approaches for both earlier diagnosis and immunomodulatory therapy of preclinical stages and early insidious clinical stage of T1D. This aim had been achieved using the following objectives:

1. Determination of the serum anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody titer by using enzyme linked immuno-sorbent assay (ELISA).
2. Detection of the serum islet antigen-2 antibody by using ELISA.
3. Detection the serum connecting peptide level by using ELISA.
4. Detection of serum total antioxidant capacity by using 2, 2'-azino-bis-3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid (ABTS) method.
5. Determination the serum expression level of miRNA-25 and miRNA-375 by using reverse transcriptase quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) technology.

Chapter Two

Literature Review

2.1 Definition of Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus

Type 1 diabetes mellitus is an autoimmune disease characterized by β -cells destruction due to autoimmune processes, which is reflected by the appearance of the pancreatic auto-Abs. The destruction of these cells implies a progressive, irreversible loss of the endogenous insulin production, leading to daily treatment with exogenous insulin. Type 1 diabetes is usually associated with the presence of anti-GAD, islet cell or insulin Abs which identify the autoimmune processes that lead to β -cells destruction. Eventually, all T1D patients will require insulin therapy to maintain normal glycaemia (Habtmu, 2015).

2.2 Classification of Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus

Several lines of evidence have suggested that autoimmunity is not the only cause of β -cells destruction. Studies have described young patients who were presented with the abrupt onset of symptoms of hyperglycemia and who were prone to the development of ketoacidosis (which is characteristic of patients with T1D) but did not have insulinitis on either biopsy or autopsy. Furthermore, evidence of an autoimmune etiology is found in about 95% of the patients with newly diagnosed T1D but the remaining 5% have no known etiologies and lack defined markers of autoimmunity (American diabetes association, 2008).

The American Diabetes Association (ADA) and the World Health Organization (WHO) have proposed that T1D can be subdivided into autoimmune (immune-mediated) diabetes (type 1A) and idiopathic diabetes with β -cells destruction (type 1B) (American diabetes association, 2008).

2.3 Epidemiology

Type 1 diabetes mellitus is the most frequently encountered chronic disease of childhood. It has been reported that the incidence of T1D

among children is increasing worldwide. Differing data related to T1D incidence in childhood have been published. This variability in the incidence of T1D is explained by ethnic background, geographical region, socioeconomic development, age, and climate (Demirbilek and Özbek, 2013).

Type 1 diabetes represents around 10% of all cases of diabetes, affecting approximately 20 million people worldwide (Ozougwu *et al.*, 2013). In general, countries in Europe and North America have either high or intermediate incidences. The incidence in Africa is generally intermediate and that in Asia is low, with the notable exception of Kuwait (Forouhi and Wareham, 2014).

The incidence of T1D varies significantly between countries with the highest incidence being reported in Northern Europe and the lowest in China and Venezuela. The majority of studies showed a relatively high incidence of T1D with an increasing trend. However, there is dearth of data from Iraq (Patterson *et al.*, 2014).

Recent studies showed intermediate incidence of T1D in Iraq. In general, the Iraq incidence was similar to that of Turkey, and higher than Jordan, and Iran, and lower than Kuwait, and Saudi Arabia. Obviously, data on genetic and environmental risk factors for T1D are needed to provide a better explanation for the difference in incidence between these neighboring countries which might share a common genetic and ethnic background (Almahfoodh *et al.*, 2017).

The incidence of T1D also varies with season, being highest in autumn and winter (Moltchanova *et al.*, 2009). In most studies, a seasonal variation in onset of T1D has been observed in children, with the highest incidence occurring during the winter months and the lowest occurring during the summer months. This finding may result from winter months

having higher rates of viral infections, which cause metabolic stress that exceeds the ability of the residual β -cells mass to produce insulin sufficient to maintain euglycemia (Gregory *et al.*, 2013).

2.4 Risks Factors

2.4.1 Race and Ethnicity

The prevalence of diabetes (all forms) was reviewed and the worldwide prevalence for all age groups was estimated to be 2.8%. T1D is much less prevalent than T2D and this form of diabetes has been noted for its peak incidence at childhood and adolescence, although the demographic pattern is changing in view of the emergence of T2D among adolescents (Maahs *et al.*, 2010).

The incidence of T1D is highest in the temperate regions and declines progressively towards the equator. High prevalence is noted within populations from these regions even when distributed in other parts of the world. A trend of a small gradual increase in incidence of T1D has been noted globally, although the underlying causes for this secular trend are not clear (Thaker and Barton, 2012).

In cross-sectional studies of adolescents and young adults, glycaemic control differs by racial and ethnic subgroups. In longitudinal studies, non-white youth with T1D have increased markers of poor prognosis at diagnosis and 3 years following diagnosis, including higher hemoglobin (Hb) A_{1c} levels, more frequent diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA), and severe hypoglycemia (Kahkoska *et al.*, 2018).

Type 1 diabetes is associated with other autoimmune conditions as hypothyroidism, hypoadrenalism, pernicious anaemia, autoimmune hepatitis, and rheumatoid arthritis in about 5%–15% of cases. Ethnic differences between the incidences of these autoimmune conditions

among people with T1D have not been reported (Kashem and Binstadt, 2017).

Type 1 diabetes is a rare manifestation of autoimmune polyendocrinopathy-candidiasis-ectodermal dystrophy (APECED) that occurs in approximately 1%–18% of patients. Its prevalence is higher among Finnish patients than among patients of Middle Eastern, Eastern or Western European ancestry. Given the variation of disease manifestation amongst different ethnic groups, it was initially hypothesized that various other factors such as human leukocyte antigen (HLA) risk alleles and environmental exposures predisposed Finnish patients to higher rates of T1D (Kashem and Binstadt, 2017).

2.4.2 Age

Type 1 diabetes is the major type of diabetes in youth, accounting for $\geq 85\%$ of all diabetes cases in youth < 20 years of age worldwide. In general, the incidence rate increases from birth and peaks between the ages of 10–14 years during puberty. Registries in Europe suggest that incident rates of T1D were highest in the youngest age-group (0–4 years). Incidence rates decline after puberty and appear to stabilize in young adulthood (15–29 years). The incidence of T1D in adults is lower than in children, although approximately one quarter of persons with T1D is diagnosed as adults (Maahs *et al.*, 2010).

2.4.3 Sex

Although most common autoimmune diseases disproportionately affect females, on average girls and boys are equally affected with T1D in young populations. A distinctive pattern has been observed such that regions with a high incidence of T1D (populations of European origin) have a male excess, whereas regions with a low incidence (populations of non-European origin) report a female excess. Many reports indicate an

excess of T1D cases in male adults after the pubertal years (male-female ratio ≥ 1.5) in populations of European origin (Soltesz *et al.*, 2007 and Maahs *et al.*, 2010).

2.4.4 Seasonal Variation

Previous studies demonstrated seasonality in the time of clinical presentation of T1D, although a consistent and integrated picture on the actual seasonality of the disease has not been established. It has been suggested that there is also a relationship between factors such as infections and vitamin D levels, and the seasonality of T1D. A meta-analysis of the data on seasonal variation in diabetes in 53 countries has suggested that seasonality in the diagnosis of T1D is indeed a real phenomenon and that this seasonality pattern appears to be related to the geographical position, at least as far as the northern/southern hemisphere is concerned. However, data on many regions of the world are still lacking (Kalliora *et al.*, 2011).

2.4.5 Genetic Susceptibility

Almost one half of monozygotic twins of patients with diabetes mellitus (DM) 1A develop diabetes. The concordance of monozygotic (50%) and dizygotic (5%) twins for DM1A differs dramatically. The probability of a monozygotic twin living in different environmental conditions to develop to diabetes decreases with the duration of discordance, but twins can become concordant more than 40 years after the development of diabetes in their twin sibling. The risk for diabetes of a dizygotic twin is more or less similar to the risk of a twin of a patient with diabetes (5%). Thus, the shared environment of dizygotic twins does not appear substantially enhance the development of diabetes. Expression of anti-islet auto-Abs is much greater for monozygotic twins as compared to dizygotic twins. The

majority of monozygotic twins of DM1A patients expressing anti-islet auto-Abs progresses to diabetes (Kantárová and Buc, 2007).

It has been shown that FDRs of patients with T1D have at least 10 times higher relative risk of T1D than in the general population. Until now, detection of β -cells auto-Abs represents a relevant clinical tool for prediction of T1D and an established risk factor for T1D development among FDRs (Milicic *et al.*, 2014). Familial clustering of T1D is a conspicuous feature; the risk of developing T1D is 8–15 folds higher in FDRs and two fold in second degree relatives. Despite this, the vast majority of children are diagnosed with the sporadic form of diabetes. The proportion of children with an affected FDRs at the time of diagnosis is; 10–12%, and after decades of follow-up, this frequency increases to 20% (Parkkola *et al.*, 2013).

Relatives of T1D patients have a high risk of developing the disease; siblings have a greater risk than offspring, and there is a high concordance rate among identical twins. This genetic predisposition is determined by the balance between susceptibility and resistance alleles. Among various factors the major histocompatibility complex (MHC) glycoproteins are very important in the recognition of the tissues by the immune system (Zhang and Eisenbarth, 2011).

Susceptibility to T1D is most strongly determined by *DQB1* and *I-A β* equivalent chain allele for MHC in mice that encode serine, alanine, or valine at position 57 on both chromosomes. In contrast, *DQ β* and *I-A β* in mice at position 57 aspartic acid positive alleles mediate resistance to T1D. To some extent, resistance is also mediated by *DR β 1* and *I-E β* in mice expressing aspartic acid at position 57 or glutamine at position 74. It has been suggested that *HLA-DQ* and *HLA-DR* polymorphism affects the susceptibility to T1D through the selectively affecting nature of the

peptides presented to T-cells. One copy (allele) of the DR3 or DR4 is found commonly in the general population. Individuals, susceptible to T1D, inherit two alleles DR3/DR3, DR4/DR4 or the high risk DR3/DR4 combination. Heterogeneity in these alleles may increase or decrease the disease risk (Precechtelova *et al.*, 2014).

Since the first association of MHC and T1D, a number of other non-MHC-related genes and immune mediators have been associated with T1D. Such genes include the insulin gene (controls glucose levels in the blood), CTLA4 (down-regulates T-cell proliferation and cytokine production), protein tyrosine phosphatase N22 gene (plays a role in T-cell receptor signaling), interleukin (IL)-2 receptor α (Its necessary for suppressing T-cell response), and interferon induced with helicase C domain 1 (*IFIH1*) gene (Precechtelova *et al.*, 2014).

Nejentsev *et al.*, (2009) identified four variations in the *IFIH1* gene, which might be associated with reduced risk of developing T1D. The helicase enzyme *IFIH1* triggers the secretion of interferons (IFN) in response to viral infection. The interferon-regulating factor 7-driven inflammatory network genes (present in monocytes and regulated by viral responses) also contribute to the risk of T1D.

Different non-MHC candidate gene products related to T1D involving the cytokine pathways include; IL-12B (drives the differentiation of CD4⁺ T-cells into Th1 cells), 2'-5'-oligoadenylate synthetase 1 (enzyme involved in the innate immune response induced by IFN against viral infections), small ubiquitin-like modifier 4 (polymorphism in this gene leads to activation of nuclear factor kappa B), paired box gene 4 (Plays a role in tissue development and is found on pancreatic islet cells), protein tyrosine phosphatase N2 gene (regulates pro-inflammatory cytokines), regulatory and pro-inflammatory T-cells and macrophage-related

cytokines including IFN- γ (cytokine involved in the inflammatory responses), tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α (stimulates inflammatory reactions and phagocytosis), IL-4 (induces differentiation of naive T-cells to T-helper (Th) cells, but suppresses INF- γ and IL-2 producing Th1 cells) and IL-10 (down-regulates expression of MHC II Ags and Th1 cytokines and is involved in cell mediated and cytotoxic inflammatory response), and C-type lectin domain family 16 (plays a role in the Ag uptake) (Heinig *et al.*, 2010).

Epigenetics may be defined as the study of the heritable changes in gene expression that occurs without modification of the deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) sequence, by mechanisms that include DNA methylation, a variety of noncoding RNAs, and enzymatically catalyzed posttranslational histone modifications (Jiménez-Chillarón *et al.*, 2012).

Several classes of small RNA can regulate genes by targeting transcripts in the cytoplasm, such as miRNAs, small interfering RNAs, repeat-associated RNAs, and germline-specific RNAs (Castel and Martienssen, 2013). The human genome encodes numerous noncoding molecules. Binding of miRNAs to 3' untranslated regions (UTRs) of target mRNA is consistent with a role for miRNAs as key negative regulators of gene expression, involved in the control of cellular processes and disease pathogenesis. The ability of noncoding RNA molecules to associate with 3' UTRs of target mRNAs and to repress their translation has been suggested to be necessary for proper β -cells development and function. During the initial stages of T1D, β -cells are submitted to diverse types of stress stimuli, causing dysfunction and death that may be associated with modifications in miRNA localization, potentially resulting in β -cells dysfunction (Guay *et al.*, 2012).

2.4.6 Environmental Factors

Epidemiological studies have identified that environmental factors operating early in life appear to trigger the immune mediated process in genetically susceptible individuals. The environmental triggers which initiate pancreatic β -cells destruction remain largely unknown. Nutritional factors that have been investigated include; cow's milk, breast feeding, wheat gluten, and vitamins D and E. Evidence regarding early introduction of cow's milk (or protective effects of breast milk consumption) in infants contributing to the development of childhood T1D is equivocal and may depend on genetic susceptibility. Timing of introduction of cereals/gluten or other foods to the infant diet has been suggested to alter risk for autoimmunity and development of T1D. Increased use of vitamin D supplementation during infancy has been associated with reduced risk for childhood T1D. Increased maternal consumption of vitamin D during pregnancy has also been associated with decreased risk of islet autoimmunity in the offspring. A protective association was observed for serum alpha tocopherol in relation to T1D. Despite these intriguing associations, there is little firm evidence of the significance of nutritional factors in the etiology of T1D (Maahs *et al.*, 2010). The mechanisms of action of different nutritional constituents that may play a role in the development of β -cells autoimmunity are largely unknown. It also remains to be defined whether these exposures, or lack thereof initiate β -cells autoimmunity or promote or accelerate an ongoing process (Majeed and Hassan, 2011).

Environmental factors playing a role in the pathogenesis of T1D may differ substantially from population to population. More specifically, disease incidence in one geographical area may differ from another because of different exposures to a given risk factor or because of

difference between population genetic susceptibilities to that risk factor (Majeed and Hassan, 2011).

Although the etiologic role of viral infections in human T1D is controversial; coxsackie virus B (CVB) 3, CVB4, cytomegalovirus (CMV), rubella, and mumps can infect human β -cells (Majeed and Hassan, 2011). The studies revealed that the viral infections are considered as the major candidates for the development of the T1D disorder. From past several decades the association of viral etiology with diabetes has been studied. The association of the viruses with T1D was studied including; CMV, parvovirus, encephalomyocarditis virus and retroviruses (Manderwad, 2017).

Literature revealed that the T1D has been found to be associated with the enterovirus. Studies including the meta-analysis found the significant association between T1D and enteroviruses and confirmed using the application of molecular techniques. The presence of coxsackie virus higher titers of the neutralizing Abs in serum found in the recent onset diabetic patients. The increase in the rate of the autoimmunity has been found to be high in diabetic cases and has been associated with the enteroviruses. Studies revealed that the enterovirus is involved in the initiation of the islet autoimmunity as well as progression to the glycemetic stage (Manderwad, 2017).

2.5 Pathogenesis

A key step in the generation of immune tolerance is Ags presentation by the antigen-presenting cells (APC) to T and B lymphocytes. In a functional immune system, the capacity to distinguish between what is self and what is not self is fundamental. However, this capability for recognition is lost when central tolerance mechanisms fail which leads to the development and expansion of self-reactive effector cells (Torre and

Lernmark, 2010). In T1D, progressive infiltration of self-reactive immune cells belonging to the innate and the adaptive immune system into the islets of Langerhans constitutes a phenomenon known as “insulitis” that represents the seal of autoimmunity (Veld, 2011).

Initial infiltration of the islets requires auto-Ags recognition by the dendritic cells (DCs) and macrophages, which are professional APC. Auto-Ags include; insulin, GAD, protein tyrosine phosphatase (PTP), insulinoma-associated Ag 2 (IA-2), zinc transporter 8 protein (ZnT8), pancreatic and duodenal homeobox 1, also known as insulin promoter factor 1, chromogranin A, and islet amyloid polypeptide (Han *et al.*, 2013 and Rojas *et al.*, 2018).

Antigen-presenting cells take up β -cells-related auto-Ags and present the respective Ags to naïve T cells with the help of the MHC II molecules expressed on the APCs. Upon excitation, T cells are expanded and differentiated into functional immune cells (Zheng *et al.*, 2017).

Naïve CD4⁺ T cells eventually develop into four major phenotypes; Th1, Th2, Th17 and T regulatory (Treg) cells. Considering the importance of these cells in autoimmunity, the pathogenic contributions of Th1 cells and protective effects of Th2 cells also play crucial roles in the pathogenesis of T1D (**Figure 2.1**) (Sia, 2005 and Zheng *et al.*, 2017). The balance between Th1 and Th2 responses has also been studied intensively in humans with T1D. Analysis of peripheral blood (PB) T cells from newly diagnosed T1D individuals provided support for an IFN- γ -dominated response to islet auto-Ags, revealing that the balance between IFN- γ and IL-10 differed between patients and HC. Individuals with T1D were more likely to have auto-Ags-specific T cells producing IFN- γ alone, or to a lesser extent a mixed IFN- γ and IL-10 response,

whereas non-diabetic subjects showed a clear bias towards production of IL-10 alone (Walker and von Herrath, 2016).

Figure (2.1): Pathogenesis of type 1 diabetes: Beta-cells are damaged by various factors and the released auto-Ags are presented by APC. Then, $CD4^+$ T, $CD8^+$ T and natural killer (NK) cells are activated, and $CD4^+$ Th lymphocytes differentiate into Th1, Th2, Th17 and Tregs. Th1 cells can destroy the islet β -cells and accelerate the course of T1D via production of IL-2 and IFN- γ . IL-2 has been shown to prevent diabetes, while it can activate $CD8^+$ T cells and Tregs. In addition, IFN- γ plays a dual role in the destruction of β -cells via the signal transducer and activator of transcription-1 (STAT-1) pathway and in protection via the interferon regulatory factor-1 (IRF-1) pathway. Th2 cells mainly produce IL-4 and IL-10, which is responsible for strong Abs production; have been ascribed with a protective role. Th17 can destroy the islet β -cells by secreting IL-17. Whether Tregs play a preventive role in the pathogenesis of T1D remains a question. In addition, NK cells are involved in direct killing of β -cells through the interaction of NK cell markers, such as NKp46 and killer-cell immunoglobulin-like receptors (KIRs). Furthermore, $CD8^+$ T cells contribute to the development of T1D by secreting proteins such as Fas, and cytokines such as TNF- α and IFN- γ (Li *et al.*, 2014).

Once the APCs process the auto-Ags, the DCs migrate towards the pancreatic lymph nodes where they promote the activation of adaptive immunity through $CD4^+$ T lymphocyte activation through IL-12 releases. The DCs also promote differentiation of B lymphocytes to plasma cells, which allows for Abs release against auto-Ags of the β -cells (Li *et al.*, 2014). B lymphocytes and their products are not directly pathogenic to β -cells; emerging evidence has revealed that they could promote autoimmunity by several mechanisms including; production of auto-Abs with consequent generation of immune complexes, Ags presentation to

generate primary auto-reactive T cell responses, contribution to the maintenance of CD4⁺T cell memory or production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (Cox and Silveira, 2009).

The Th1 CD4⁺ secrete IL-2 and IFN- γ , which further stimulates DC and macrophage secretion of other cytokines such as IL-1 β and TNF- α that in turn promotes CD8⁺ cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTLs) migration. This leads to a progressively activated macrophage and T cell accumulation around and inside the islets (Mallone *et al.*, 2011). Additionally, inflammatory cytokines induce overexpression of MHC class I molecules on the β -cells and MHC class II on the APC, increasing auto-Ags presentation, which raises the susceptibility of β -cells to attacks from self-reactive T lymphocytes (Morran *et al.*, 2008). Once activated, these self-reactive cells unleash an immune response through the release of proinflammatory cytokines that will bind with receptors located on the β -cells surface and that will activate intracellular signals that will end in the death of the β -cells (Bending *et al.*, 2012).

Regulatory T cells are a heterogeneous subgroup of CD4⁺ T cells that intervene by averting the proliferation and activation of auto-reactive effector T (T-effs) cells and inducing immune tolerance, thereby leading to a decline in inflammatory responses (Jaberi *et al.*, 2015). T regs exert their immunosuppressive functions mainly via four mechanisms: cell-to-cell contact, secretion of immunosuppressive cytokines, killing or modification of APCs and competition for growth factors. T reg deficiency may deprive or blunt their immunosuppressive capabilities, thereby accelerating autoimmunity (Sharma *et al.*, 2016).

Th17 is another subset of Th cells that is characterized by secretion of the proinflammatory cytokines IL-17, IL-17F, IL-22 and IL-21. IL-17 is a key cytokine with the ability to induce the synthesis of other

inflammatory cytokines and chemokines (Shao *et al.*, 2012). Th17 cells exert immunological functions in T1D mainly through the following pathways: (1) Th17 cells counteract Treg cells to expand and disturb the Teff/Treg cell ratio, which allows the development of T1D, (2) Th17 cells may convert to diabetogenic T cells and enhance the islet-destruction effects in T1D and (3) Th17 cells can stimulate CD8⁺ CTLs, thereby contributing to the development of T1D. A ‘balanced auto-reactive set-point’ (Th1/Th17 vs Treg/Th2 cells) is a key determinant of the pathological outcome in T1D (Marwaha *et al.*, 2012).

The ways in which β -cells die may determine whether immune responses are activated. Necrotic cell death is considered to be a likely mechanism whereby CTLs, including those reactive with diabetes Ags, cause killing. Findings from pancreatic biopsies and post-mortem studies of whole organs from islet donors are consistent with this mechanism, showing a predominance of infiltrating CD8⁺ T cells and macrophages which mediate necrosis (Wilcox *et al.*, 2016). Necrosis can occur following the release of cytolytic granules from T cells that contain granzymes and perforin, which act on the β -cells membrane. Common mediators of necrotic cell death include calcium and reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Zhao *et al.*, 2015).

In particular, ROS results in mitochondrial injury as well as loss of both cell membrane integrity and ion balance through protein damage, lipid peroxidation and oxidative DNA damage (Zhao *et al.*, 2015). These factors lead to opening of mitochondrial permeability transition pores, which in turn disrupts oxidative phosphorylation and adenosine triphosphate (ATP) production. Deoxyribonucleic acid damage leads to poly (adenosine diphosphate (ADP)-ribose) polymerase (Pol) activation

and increased nicotinamide-adenine dinucleotide (NAD) consumption and thus reduced ATP production (Wilcox *et al.*, 2016).

The serine/threonine kinase receptor-interacting protein 1 (RIP1) is another initiator of necrotic cell death that is induced by ligand-receptor interactions. Adenosine triphosphate depletion plays a crucial role as an initiating factor in this process (Wali *et al.*, 2014).

Other factors including the lysosomal enzyme acid-sphingomyelinase, cytosolic phospholipase A and calpains, Ca²⁺-dependent cysteine protease family, all of which contribute to cell membrane destabilization (Wilcox *et al.*, 2016).

Necrotic cells release cellular contents including factors, such as High Mobility Group Box 1 proteins (HMGB-1), Heat Shock Proteins (HSP), uric acid and pro-inflammatory cytokines, which lead to recognition and engulfment by phagocytes and immunologic activity. Ultimately, necrotic death of β -cells may lead to a “feed-forward” mechanism whereby the released factors stimulate immune responses even after tolerance has been established or the immune response has been treated (Dorn, 2013).

Others way of β -cells death is apoptosis. Many mechanisms are included; **i**) expression of the apoptosis stimulating fragment (Fas) and its ligand (Fas-L) on the surface of CD8⁺ T-activated cells and β -cells, respectively, **ii**) secretion of proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IFN- γ by the different immune cells infiltrated in the islets of Langerhans, **iii**) and production of ROS such as nitric oxide (NO) by macrophages, DCs, and β -cells. All of these mechanisms converge in the induction of apoptotic programmed cell death (Lightfoot *et al.*, 2012).

There are two main apoptotic signaling pathways, both involved in the death of the β -cells during the development of T1D (Rojas *et al.*, 2018); the **intrinsic pathway**, also known as the mitochondrial pathway which

is activated by different types of cell stress such as hypoxia or OS, in which proteins of the Bcl-2 family intervene (Gurzov and Eizirik, 2011). Conversely, the **extrinsic pathway** or the pathway mediated by cell death receptors initiates with the union of ligand belonging to the TNF superfamily such as TNF- α , Fas-L, and its respective receptors expressed on the surface of the β -cells that translates the apoptotic signal downstream through its cell death domain to other associated proteins (Eisenberg *et al.*, 2009). In any of the two cases, once the death signal is recognized, recruitment of the proteins in charge with executing said signal takes place. These include cysteine-aspartic proteases (caspases) (Rojas *et al.*, 2018), which are a family of proteins synthesized in their inactive form as zymogens or procaspases, each with an N-terminal domain that needs to be eliminated for their activation. Once active, they have the ability to mediate the rupture of other proteins in aspartate residues through its cysteine residue. Caspases work in a coordinated and sequential manner (Choil and Wool, 2009) in a process that leads to apoptosis. They are classified according to their activity: there are initiator caspases including caspases 2, 8, 9, and 10 which activate other caspases, and executioner caspases 3, 6, and 7 which degrade proteins vital to the cell and are responsible for the morphologic changes suffered by the β -cells. Other group of caspases including 1, 4, 5, 11, 12 and 13 are known as inflammatory caspases (Rojas *et al.*, 2018).

2.6 Stages

Human T1D arises from both genetic and environmental factors that lead to immune-mediated destruction of pancreatic β -cells and loss of β -cells function. After onset of islet autoimmunity, the disease progresses through a presymptomatic stage identified by markers of autoimmunity and glucose intolerance, or so-called dysglycemia, arising from further

loss of β -cells function and culminates ultimately with clinical symptoms and signs of diabetes (**Figure 2.2**). In children and adults, the rate of progression from onset of β -cells autoimmunity to glucose intolerance and then to symptomatic disease is variable, lasting from months to decades (**Atkinson *et al.*, 2014**).

2.6.1 Stage 1 (Autoimmunity/Normoglycemia/Presymptomatic)

Stage 1 represents individuals who have developed two or more T1D-associated islet auto-Abs but are normoglycemic. For children who were screened for genetic risk at birth and reach this stage, the 5-year and 10-year risks of symptomatic disease are approximately 44% and 70%, respectively, and the lifetime risk approaches 100%. The risk at this stage is quite similar in genetically at-risk children and in relatives of individuals with T1D (**Steck *et al.*, 2015**).

2.6.2 Stage 2 (Autoimmunity/Dysglycemia/Presymptomatic)

Stage 2, like stage 1, includes individuals with two or more islet auto-Abs but whose disease has now progressed to the development of glucose intolerance, or dysglycemia, from loss of functional β -cells mass. The 5-year risk of symptomatic disease at this stage is approximately 75%, and the lifetime risk approaches 100% (**Krischer and Type 1 Diabetes Trial Net Study Group, 2013**).

2.6.3 Stage 3 (Autoimmunity/Dysglycemia/Symptomatic)

Stage 3 represents manifestations of the typical clinical symptoms and signs of diabetes, which may include polyuria, polydipsia, weight loss, fatigue, DKA, and others (**Insel *et al.*, 2015**).

Figure (2.2): Stages of type 1 diabetes (Insel *et al.*, 2015).

Preclinical diabetes (stages 1–2) refers to the months or years preceding the clinical presentation of T1D when the following islet Abs can be detected as markers of β -cells autoimmunity (Watkins *et al.*, 2014):

- GAD65 auto-Abs.
- Tyrosine phosphatase-like IA2 and islet cell antigen (ICA) 512 auto-Abs.
- Insulin autoantibodies (IAA).
- Beta-cells-specific ZnT8 auto-Abs.

2.7 Clinical Presentation

New-onset T1D presents in the majority of pediatric patients with the classic symptoms of polyuria and polydipsia and somewhat less frequently with polyphagia and weight loss. Often, these symptoms become more apparent after an episode of enuresis or with the emergence of nocturia. Patients frequently have vague complaints, such as fatigue, and may note blurred vision. Some children have a rapid onset of

symptoms and present within days in DKA, others have a slow onset of symptoms over several months (Gregory *et al.*, 2013).

In roughly one-quarter of cases, a patient with new-onset T1D will present with DKA. These children and adolescents tend initially to have the same classic symptoms (polyuria, polydipsia, polyphagia, weight loss), which become more severe. As acidosis develops, these patients frequently lose their appetite and nausea, vomiting, and abdominal pain become the significant symptoms. To compensate for the worsening ketoacidosis, hyperpnea develops (Kussmaul respirations). If unchecked, neurologic status progressively deteriorates as acidosis and hyperosmolality worsen, and the patient progresses from drowsiness to lethargy to obtundation. Risk factors associated with an initial presentation of DKA include younger age, especially children younger than 2 years old, ethnic minority status, and lower socioeconomic and parental education levels (Wolfsdorf *et al.*, 2006 and Gregory *et al.*, 2013).

A smaller number of children and adolescents are diagnosed as having diabetes despite having none of the classic symptoms of T1D. These children usually have impaired glucose tolerance because of β -cells loss, but have not yet had overt symptoms (Gregory *et al.*, 2013).

2.8 Complications

Type 1 diabetes mellitus is a progressive disease with risk factors for both macro-vascular (coronary artery disease, peripheral arterial disease, and stroke) and micro-vascular (diabetic nephropathy, neuropathy, and retinopathy) complications. There is growing evidence that the underlying mechanisms in the pathogenesis of diabetic complications include certain genetic and epigenetic modifications, nutritional factors, and sedentary lifestyle (Kautzky *et al.*, 2016).

The central pathological mechanism in macrovascular disease is the process of atherosclerosis, which leads to narrowing of arterial walls throughout the body. Diabetes increases the risk that an individual will develop cardiovascular disease (CVD). Although the precise mechanisms through which diabetes increases the likelihood of atherosclerotic plaque formation are not completely defined, the association between the two is profound (Fowler, 2008).

Diabetic nephropathy, neuropathy, and retinopathy are the main microvascular complications induced by chronic hyperglycemia via several mechanisms such as the production of advanced glycation end products (AGEs), the creation of a proinflammatory microenvironment, and the induction of OS (Chilelli *et al.*, 2013).

Upregulation of $\alpha3\beta1$ -integrin in podocytes in early-stage diabetic nephropathy shed light on the mechanism of podocyte detachment from the glomerular basement membrane, which is considered to be a key factor in the development of diabetic nephropathy. Hyperglycemia induced production of ROS on the renin-angiotensin system and the signaling pathway of the transforming growth factor (TGF)- β . They have concluded that OS leads to the production of chronic inflammation and the glomerular and tubular hypertrophy, which characterize the early stages of diabetic nephropathy (Papatheodorou *et al.*, 2016).

The risk of developing diabetic retinopathy or other microvascular complications of diabetes depends on both the duration and the severity of hyperglycemia. Aldose reductase may participate in the development of diabetes complications. Aldose reductase is the initial enzyme in the intracellular polyol pathway. This pathway involves the conversion of glucose into glucose alcohol (sorbitol). High glucose levels increase the flux of sugar molecules through the polyol pathway, which causes

sorbitol accumulation in cells. Osmotic stress from sorbitol accumulation has been postulated as an underlying mechanism in the development of diabetic microvascular complications, including diabetic retinopathy (Fowler, 2008).

Oxidative stress may also play an important role in cellular injury from hyperglycemia. High glucose levels can stimulate free radical production and ROS formation. Growth factors, including vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), growth hormone, and TGF- β , have also been postulated to play important roles in the development of diabetic retinopathy. Vascular endothelial growth factor production is increased in diabetic retinopathy, possibly in response to hypoxia (Fowler, 2008).

Peripheral neuropathy in diabetes may manifest in several different forms, including sensory, focal/multifocal, and autonomic neuropathies. More than 80% of amputations occur after foot ulceration or injury, which can result from diabetic neuropathy. The precise nature of injury to the peripheral nerves from hyperglycemia is not known but likely is related to mechanisms such as polyol accumulation, injury from AGEs, and OS (Fowler, 2008).

2.9 Biomarkers of Beta Cells Stress/Death

In type 1 diabetes there is an immune-mediated destruction of the insulin producing pancreatic β -cells. Type 1 diabetes initiates from a break in immune tolerance and infiltration of auto-reactive T cells that target the β -cells, leading to loss of β -cells function and mass and a lifelong requirement for exogenous insulin (Lehuen *et al.*, 2010). To preserve β -cells function, a number of immunomodulatory drugs have been tested around the time of T1D clinical diagnosis. These, include anti-CD3, anti-CD20, CTLA4-Ig, and alefacept (a fusion protein combines part of an Ab with a protein that blocks the growth of some

types of T cells) have led to a moderate preservation of β -cells function (Rigby *et al.*, 2013). However, true remission from T1D, as defined by insulin independence, remains elusive. These outcomes could be explained by the low proliferative and regenerative capacity of human β -cells (Gregg *et al.*, 2012), combined with the possibility that interventions were initiated too late in the disease. In recent years, data characterizing intrinsic β -cells stress in T1D suggest that processes such as β -cells calcium dyshomeostasis, misfolded protein accumulation, OS, and endoplasmic reticulum stress become activated early during the evolution of T1D and act to either initiate immune activation through formation of neoantigens or serve to augment autoimmune-mediated β -cells death and dysfunction (Marré *et al.*, 2015). Whereas these pathways may serve as points of therapeutic intervention, focused methods to identify biomarkers that reflect an authentic signature of β -cells stress and/or death may also improve our ability to optimally time immunomodulatory and other forms of interventions in T1D. In such a paradigm, a valid signature of β -cells stress could serve as a signal to initiate immunomodulatory therapy in the pre-T1D diabetic period. Thus, interventions in the newly defined stages 1–2 of the pre-symptomatic phase of T1D offer the promise of more effective preservation of β -cells mass (Insel *et al.*, 2015).

2.9.1 Psychological Stress

Beta cell stress has been suggested as a risk factor for the development of T1D (Ludvigsson, 2006). During psychological stress and periods of rapid growth, such as infancy and puberty, the β -cells have to work hard to produce insulin. This increased insulin production may result in β -cells stress and stimulation of the autoimmune process, leading to overt diabetes. This β -cells stress hypothesis is an extension of the accelerator

hypothesis, which states that increased insulin resistance, associated with childhood overweight and obesity, creates greater insulin secretory demand on the islets, leading to acceleration of β -cells destruction and T1D. The accelerator hypothesis suggests that the increased incidence of T1D may be caused by an accelerated progression rather than by an increase in the absolute lifetime risk (Rewers and Ludvigsson, 2016).

Psychological stress may, in certain individuals, cause insulin resistance and thereby β -cells stress and diabetes-associated autoimmunity. Psychological factors that have been found to influence the development of auto-Abs, in one or two and a half year old children of the general population, include high parental stress and serious life events (Skoglund, 2011).

It has been shown that the activation of the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis during stress reaction can change the homeostasis between the two systems and alters the activity of suppressive cells (T-suppressors) that usually prevent damage to the individual (Atanackovic *et al.*, 2013). Prolonged exposure to adverse events, in fact, affects hormonal balance, metabolism and immune function. The prolonged activation of the HPA axis, in particular, increases glucocorticoid levels, causing pathologies related to hypercortisolism. Furthermore, this condition promotes the alteration of the immune function and facilitates the development of central obesity, peripheral tissue resistance to insulin and glucose intolerance. These processes, however, are not the same in all individuals and researchers have found some gender-related variations (Falco *et al.*, 2015). Accordingly, epidemiological studies indicate that severe stress often precedes the development of certain Th1-mediated autoimmune diseases. Among these, T1D is characterized by the

development of auto-Abs against islet cells in the pancreas and against insulin (Atanackovic *et al.*, 2013).

2.9.2 Autoantibodies

Auto-Abs can be detected before and at time of clinical diagnosis of T1D. Although the role of auto-Abs in the pathogenesis is debated, their presence indicates a dysregulation of the humoral immune response. Mechanisms regulating auto-Abs in T1D are not well understood as well. Other than insulin and carboxypeptidase H, all islet Ags are intracellular and are not normally secreted or expressed on the surface of the cell. The release of intracellular Ags is possibly the result of cell mediated autoimmune damage to cells, which permits such otherwise sequestered self Ags access to naive mature B lymphocytes and naive CD4 T cells. However, if the cells were to die, β -cells death might have then led to subsequent islet auto-Ags immunization (Herawati *et al.*, 2017).

Auto-Abs, called ICA, is detected in individuals with T1D and allows the clinical course of diabetes to be studied in human subjects (Orban *et al.*, 2009). Over the years the specificities of several ICA have been clarified, although some still remain unidentified. Islet cell auto-Abs recognizing islet cytoplasmic Ags were detected many years ago in newly-diagnosed T1D patients. The presence of organ-specific pancreatic auto-Abs provides evidence for T1D as an autoimmune disease (Yoon and Jun, 2005).

Of the known specificities, GAD, IA-2, insulin antigen (IA) and ZnT8 Ag are the most common target Ags. Glutamic acid decarboxylase is a biosynthesizing enzyme of the inhibitory neurotransmitter gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) and has been the most extensively studied β -cells auto-Ags (Yoon and Jun, 2005). This enzyme is expressed at high levels by pancreatic β -cells and a subpopulation of central nervous

system neurons. There are two isoforms of GAD; GAD65 and GAD67, with molecular masses of 65 kilo Daltons (kDa) and 67 kDa, respectively. In human pancreatic islet cells only the GAD65 isoform is expressed. Glutamic acid decarboxylase enzymatically converts glutamic acid to GABA in GABAergic neurons and islet β -cells. Therefore, Abs to the GAD65 isoform is used to evaluate human disease (Skoglund, 2011).

Insulinoma Ag-2 is a PTP-like protein found in cells of the pancreatic islet (Skoglund, 2011 and Chramy, 2012). Insulinoma Ag-2 is a major auto-Ag in T1D and it belongs to the PTP family which is expressed in pancreatic islets and brain tissues. The close association between IA-2A and HLA DR4 indicates that IA-2A may be a more specific marker of β -cells destruction than GAD auto-Abs. Insulinoma Ag-2 seems to be a strong predictor for development of T1D (Skoglund, 2011).

Insulinoma Ag-2, previously known as ICA-512. IA-2 are the main targets of islet cell auto-Abs. Protein is found also in nerve tissue, encoded by a gene located at chromosome 2q35. This gene encodes a 979 amino acid, enzymatic trans-membrane protein that is inactive, and the PTP-like-molecule. This Ag has no enzymatic activity for several substitutions in highly conserved sites and expressed mainly in neuroendocrine cells such as the central nervous system as well as in the islets of Langerhans cells. The residue intracellular Ag is anchored on the membrane of the insulin secretory granule, and the dominant Abs will attack the intracellular domain (amino acids 601-979) and this only occurs when there is a damage cells. The function of the Ag is not known with certainty. Experiments on mice showed the role of IA-2 in insulin secretion. IA-2A can be the complement of GADA test, since more than 90% of children have Abs to at least one of these proteins at diabetes onset. Insulinoma Ag-2 and GAD make the predominant, but not

exclusive, contribution to ICA-reactivity. The presence of IA-2A in particular, which is often associated with other Abs, confers a higher risk of rapid progression toward clinical onset than multiple Abs. It is suggested that the production of IA-2A coincides with a critical switch in disease progression, where the intracellular domain of IA-2 may only become visible to the immune system at the outer cell surface in the case of β -cells damage or dysfunction (Herawati *et al.*, 2017).

Insulin auto-Abs is directed to β chain of insulin or proinsulin, the only known β -cells specific auto-Ag. Once insulin replacement therapy begins, insulin Abs may not be a useful marker since some patients develop Abs to exogenous insulin. Antibodies specific for β -cells Ags are present with increased frequency among individuals recently diagnosed with T1D. Their presence confirms a diagnosis of type 1A diabetes (Pihoker *et al.*, 2005).

Zinc Transporter-8 is a multi-spanning transmembrane protein belonging to a large cation efflux family, which is an auto-Ag in T1D. Auto-Abs to the C-terminal part of ZnT8 has shown a strong relation to disease development. Zinc Transporter-8 auto-Abs has been found in about 60% of children with new onset T1D. In the first report, ZnT8 auto-Abs was found in 26% of T1D patients previously classified as auto-Ab negative. Both the levels and the prevalence of ZnT8 auto-Abs increase with age, and the Abs appear frequently in children by 3 years of age. Zinc Transporter-8 auto-Abs usually precedes the disease by many years and emerges often after GAD auto-Abs and IAA (Wenzlau *et al.*, 2007).

Auto-Abs production appears in advance (months to years) of the metabolic changes of T1D and can be used to predict disease. Since normal individuals may produce islet specific auto-Abs, the predictive value is enhanced greatly when screening is limited to FDRs of a

proband: the presence of 2 or more distinct auto-Abs specificities is highly predictive of future T1D (Zhang and Eisenbarth, 2011).

2.9.3 Connecting Peptide

Insulin, one of the major auto-Ags in T1D, is a hormone that regulates energy and glucose metabolism in the body. The blood glucose level is lowered by insulin, through the acceleration of glucose transportation into cells. Insulin is secreted by β -cells, which constitute about 70% of the pancreatic islet cells. The protein consists of 51 amino acids and is encoded on chromosome 11p15 (Skoglund, 2011). The insulin molecule is a heterodimer consisting of an A and a B chain of 21 and 30 amino acids, respectively, linked by two disulfide bridges (**Figure 2.3**). Insulin is synthesized as pre-proinsulin by the β -cells of the pancreas, and after cleavage of an NH_2 -terminal sequence, proinsulin is formed. After folding of proinsulin into its correct secondary and tertiary structure, the 5.8 kDa insulin protein is formed by proteolytic cleavage and removal of the C-peptide, which is a large peptide in the middle of the proinsulin molecule (Eisenbarth, 2008).

Connecting peptide concentration is widely accepted as an indicator of endogenous insulin secretion (Saisho, 2016). Low or vanished C-peptide levels are indicative of advancing T1D after diagnosis, and undetectable C-peptide is usually observed after ~1 year of disease duration. Yet, even small amounts of residual β -cells function confer fewer complications in most studies. The strongest evidence, however, finds that while higher and sustained levels of C-peptide are most beneficial, even modest levels of β -cells function in some with long-term disease are associated with lower rates of hypoglycemia and lower incidence of retinopathy and nephropathy (Panero *et al.*, 2009).

Figure (2.3): The structure of proinsulin and insulin: Proinsulin is formed from pre-proinsulin and after removal of the C-peptide the insulin protein is formed, consisting of an A and a B chain of 21 and 30 amino acids, respectively (Skoglund, 2011).

The findings raise questions about how long insulin production persists, whether β -cells functioning are fully maintained, and what personal or disease factors predict residual β -cells function. Connecting peptide is a useful and widely used method of assessing pancreatic β -cells function (Kulkarni and Patil, 2016). After cleavage of proinsulin, insulin and the 31-amino-acid peptide (C-peptide) are produced in equal amounts. So why is C-peptide testing preferable to insulin as a guide to β -cells function? The degradation rate of C-peptide in the body is slower than that of insulin (half-life of 20–30 min, compared with the half-life of insulin of just 3–5 min), which affords a more stable test window of fluctuating β -cells response. Half of all insulin secreted by the pancreas is metabolized in the liver by first-pass metabolism, whereas C-peptide has negligible hepatic clearance. Connecting peptide is cleared in the peripheral circulation at a constant rate, whereas insulin is cleared variably making direct measurement less consistent. In insulin-treated patients with diabetes, measurement of C-peptide also avoids the pitfall of cross-reaction of assay between exogenous and endogenous insulin (Yosten *et al.*, 2014). Increasing evidence suggests that C-peptide may

also be useful in predicting future levels of glycemic control, response to hypoglycemic agents, and risk of future diabetes complications.

2.9.4 Oxidative Stress

The biological systems living in aerobic conditions are exposed to oxidants, either generated intentionally or as byproducts. Generally, these oxidants occur in two categories consisting of paramagnetic free radicals: ROS and reactive nitrogen species (RNS). Reactive oxygen species is a collective term used to describe the chemical species that are formed upon incomplete reduction of oxygen and includes; superoxide anion, hydrogen peroxide, and hydroxyl radical. In contrast, RNS refers to all the oxidation states and reactive adducts of nitrogenous nitric oxide synthase products, from NO to nitroxyl, S-nitrosothiol, and peroxynitrite. Reactive oxygen species and RNS, previously considered to be toxic agents capable to damage molecules, have indeed critical biological functions essential for normal physiology. All these species are able to initiate or mediate many enzyme- and gene-dependent reactions in both physiological and pathophysiological processes. Overproduction or deficiency of ROS and/or RNS may result in impaired homeostasis and associated pathology. Thus, it is widely believed that multiple pathogenic mechanisms involve disequilibrium in the redox balance as the final common pathway ([Autreaux and Toledano, 2007](#)).

Challenges in the development of therapeutic intervene for T1D is the identification of certain pathways and targets that participate in aggressive immune responses and/or β -cells death. Attention is increasing for OS and their associated pathways within the β -cells that may risk the β -cells to death upon activation of autoimmunity in T1D ([Maganti *et al.*, 2016](#)). Oxidative stress is a condition where the increased formation of free radicals overwhelms the available antioxidant capacity ([Powers *et*](#)

al., 2011). Impairment in the oxidant/antioxidant equilibrium creates a condition known as OS. There is a complex interaction between antioxidants and oxidants such as ROS, which modulates the generation of OS. Oxidative stress takes place in a cellular system when the generation of ROS increases and overwhelms the body's antioxidant capacity and defenses. If the free radicals are not removed by the cellular antioxidants, they may attack and damage lipids, carbohydrates, proteins and nucleic acids (Birben *et al.*, 2012).

Oxidative stress is involved in many human diseases, such as atherosclerosis, cardiovascular and neurological diseases as well as in aging (Powers *et al.*, 2011). Oxidative stress is also participant in the development and progression of diabetes and its complications (Bashan *et al.*, 2009). Indeed, disruption of the physiological free radicals homeostasis has been implicated in the impairment of β -cells function (Drews *et al.*, 2010). Antioxidant enzymes and other associated molecules within the host cells and tissues are considered as the first line of defense against ROS. It has been documented that the pancreatic islet is among the least possessed tissues in terms of intrinsic antioxidant enzyme expression and function, including superoxide dismutases, catalase, and glutathione peroxidase. Little information are available about the expression of antioxidant enzymes within islet cell subset. However, expression of antioxidant enzymes catalase and glutathione peroxidase in human is lower β -cells than α -cells, a fact that could, at least in part, account for the more intense oxidative damage and lower viability of β -cells following exposure to oxidative and nitrosative stress observed (Miki *et al.*, 2018).

Regulated production of free radicals, however, participates in several physiological processes, being also beneficial (Vollaard *et al.*, 2005). In

fact, free radicals act as a double-edged sword in modulating insulin signaling, being required for insulin to exert its physiological action, but also being implicated in the pathogenesis of insulin resistance (Bashan *et al.*, 2009). There are multiple likely sources of ROS and RNS, especially in diabetes, including; glucose autoxidation, glycation of proteins, consumption of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate hydrogen (NADPH) through the polyol pathway, and activation of protein kinase C (Golbidi *et al.*, 2012). In T1D, the infiltration of the pancreatic islets by immune cells mediates β -cells dysfunction and destruction by production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, ROS and RNS resulting in insulin deficiency (Pirot *et al.*, 2008).

Previous studies reported that OS participates in the progression and pathogenesis of secondary diabetic complications. This includes impairment of insulin action and elevation of the complications incidence (Ceriello, 2006). Furthermore, there is evidence for the role of ROS and OS in the development of T1D complications including retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy, and accelerated coronary artery diseases (Niedowicz and Daleke, 2005). It has been also reported that OS induced by ROS and RNS is critically involved in the impairment of β -cells function, and thus play a role in the pathology of T1D. Islet β -cells are highly susceptible to OS because of their reduced levels of endogenous antioxidants (Pitocco *et al.*, 2013). With decreased antioxidant capacity, β -cells are extremely sensitive towards OS. Cell metabolism and potassium channels (adenosine-5'-triphosphate) in β -cells are important targets for ROS and other oxidants. The alterations of potassium channel (adenosine-5'-triphosphate) activity by the oxidants, is crucial for oxidant-induced dysfunction as genetic ablation of potassium channels

(adenosine-5'-triphosphate) attenuates the effects of OS on β -cells function (Drews *et al.*, 2010).

Oxidative stress may reduce insulin sensitivity and damage the β -cells within the pancreas. The ROS produced by OS can penetrate through cell membranes and cause damage to the β -cells of pancreas (Chen *et al.*, 2005). Reactive oxygen species produced from free fatty acids can cause mitochondrial DNA damage and impaired pancreatic β -cells function (Rachek *et al.*, 2006). Mitochondrial and NO-derived ROS have been implicated in β -cells destruction and subsequently T1D. Furthermore, increased glucose can cause rapid induction of the Krebs cycle within the β -cells mitochondria, leading to augmented ROS production (Newsholme *et al.*, 2007). The superoxide leaked from the mitochondria can contribute to the formation of hydrogen peroxide which may play a role in uncoupling glucose metabolism from insulin secretion (Pomytkin, 2012).

In clinical practice, analytical measurement of OS markers has been difficult, due to the short half-life of the majority of these compounds (few seconds) and to the applicability of the determination methods. Blood and urine samples are the eligible biological materials for assessment of the oxidant and antioxidant status in humans; however, some antioxidant enzymes and metabolites of OS have also been determined in tissue extracts (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2008). A variety of methods, including ELISA, high pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC), spectroscopy, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, immunoblotting, electroelution fractionation, isoelectric focusing, voltammetry, and electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy have been applied for determination of metabolites of OS (Palmieri and Sblendorio, 2007). A dynamic indicator of OS *in vivo* is the quantification of the redox state of glutathione in tissues and/or plasma. This can be determined

biochemically or by HPLC. Lipid peroxidation is one of the most widely used indicators for determining the cellular oxidant status (Pitocco *et al.*, 2013).

Antioxidant capacity includes endogenous compounds like bilirubin, uric acid, superoxide dismutases, catalase, and glutathione peroxidase, as well as exogenous substances, such as carotenoids, tocopherols, ascorbate, and bioflavonoids. These antioxidant molecules are subdivided into three categories: enzyme systems, small molecules and proteins. Total antioxidant capacity measures either the combination of both small molecule antioxidants and proteins or small molecules alone. An enhanced chemiluminescence assay is commonly used to measure the non-enzymatic TAC, but it is expensive and time-consuming, therefore, commercial colorimetric kits are frequently preferred (Pitocco *et al.*, 2013).

2.9.5 Micro-RNAs (miRNA)

Micro-RNAs are endogenous, evolutionarily conserved and short (21–23 nucleotides) non-coding RNAs that function as key modulators of gene expression in a posttranscriptional manner. The majority of miRNA-coding genes are located in the introns of protein-coding genes. However, these genes can also be localized in exons, intergenic regions, or 5' and 3' UTRs. Micro-RNA genes are transcribed in the nucleus primarily by RNA Pol II to produce primary miRNAs (pri-miRNAs), which have multiple stem-loop structures. Most pri-miRNAs are processed to produce miRNA precursors (pre-miRNAs) by the Drosha–DGCR8 microprocessor complex (canonical pathway). Then, the pre-miRNAs are transported to the cytoplasm and further cleaved by the RNase III endonuclease Dicer to generate mature miRNAs (Figure 2.4) (Ross *et al.*, 2007).

The mature miRNAs can be loaded into the RNA induced silencing complex (RISC) assembly, which subsequently mediates the regulatory functions of miRNAs (Ross *et al.*, 2007).

Generally, miRNAs exert their functions via binding with the 3' UTRs of their target genes, resulting in translational silencing or direct mRNA degradation (Ross *et al.*, 2007).

Interestingly, recent findings have revealed that miRNAs may also modulate gene expression in a positive manner. A representative paradigm is that miRNA-10a can bind to the 5' UTR of ribosomal protein mRNAs and enhance their translation. In addition, miRNA-21 has been found to directly target mitochondrial cytochrome b (mt-Cytb) and positively regulate mt-Cytb translation (Li *et al.*, 2016). Micro-RNAs play important roles in the normal maintenance of cell homeostasis and biological functions (Garo and Murugaiyan, 2016).

Figure (2.4): The biogenesis of micro-RNAs: Micro-RNAs are initially transcribed by Pol II as pri-miRNA transcripts which are processed by Drosha to generate pre-miRNAs. Pre-miRNAs are exported from nucleus to cytoplasm by exportin 5 (EXPO5). The Dicer complex is recruited to pre-miRNAs to remove the stem loop from pre-miRNAs, and then mature miRNAs which is one strand of the miRNA duplex are incorporated into RISC. Within the RISC, miRNAs bind to complementary sequences of target mRNAs to repress their translation or induce their degradation (Jung and Suh, 2014).

Aberrant miRNA expression is associated with many pathological conditions in humans, including cancers, neurodegenerative disorders, infectious diseases and autoimmune diseases. Recently, a growing number of studies have implicated miRNAs in the pathogenesis of autoimmune T1D (Garo and Murugaiyan, 2016).

In humans, over 2500 miRNAs have been cataloged, and it is estimated that collectively these miRNAs regulate approximately 60% of protein-coding genes. Whereas miRNAs are generated intracellularly and largely function in a cell-autonomous fashion, they can be selectively secreted extracellularly in microvesicles or exosomes and thereby transmit their regulatory functions to other cell types. Micro-RNAs have accordingly been regarded as potential circulating biomarkers that reflect activities of their cells of origin (Mirmira *et al.*, 2016). The systemic stability of miRNAs relative to other RNA species allows for their measurement in a variety of biological fluids, including blood, urine, saliva, cerebrospinal fluid, milk, seminal fluid, and amniotic fluid, making them prime targets for biomarker discovery (Weber *et al.*, 2010).

2.9.5.1 Micro-RNAs and Immune Response Modulation

Accumulating evidence has shown that miRNAs are important participants in the control of the delicate immune system equilibrium. Micro-RNAs function as key modulators of immune responses mainly through the regulation of immune cells differentiation, development, activation and functions. During T-cell development, deletion of Dicer in immature thymocytes leads to a drastic reduction in total thymocyte numbers, with a significant reduction in the more mature double-positive (CD4⁺CD8⁺) and single-positive (CD4⁺ or CD8⁺) thymocytes probably as a result of increased cell death and attenuated proliferation (Cobb *et al.*, 2005). In the case of Th cell differentiation, CD4⁺ T cells lacking Dicer

fail to evolve into the Th2 phenotype due to a bias toward Th1 differentiation and their inability to prevent IFN- γ production (Muljo *et al.*, 2005). In addition, the specific overexpression or deletion of individual miRNA genes affects T-cell development. The miRNA-17-92 family is hyperexpressed in T precursor cells, but the expression levels of these family members decrease concomitant with T-cell maturation (Ventura *et al.*, 2008).

CD4⁺ T cells isolated from miRNA-155-deficient mice are apparently biased toward Th2 differentiation and are accompanied by the secretion of Th2 cytokines (Thai *et al.*, 2007).

Regulatory T cells with specifically deleted miRNAs due to Dicer or Drosha ablation can develop an early fatal onset of autoimmunity (Chong *et al.*, 2008). Individual miRNA-deficient Tregs are predisposed to have an inadequate ability to underscore their functional relevance, such as inhibition of miRNA-155 can disturb Treg development and functions (Lu *et al.*, 2009) and miRNA-21 and miRNA-31 which regulate Treg development by changing Foxp3 expression (Rouas *et al.*, 2009). Several miRNAs have been reported to promote Th17 cell development as miRNA-326 which facilitates Th17 development and accelerates the progression of autoimmunity and inhibiting certain negative modulator of Th17 differentiation (Du *et al.*, 2009).

In addition, the regulatory roles of miRNAs are crucial for early B-cell development. Deletion of Dicer has been demonstrated to halt the pro- to pre-B-cell transition (Koralov *et al.*, 2008). Micro-RNAs also exert important effects on NK cell and APC development and functions (Zhu *et al.*, 2013).

2.9.5.2 Micro-RNAs and Type 1 Diabetes

Different miRNA expression patterns have been observed within specific T-cell subtypes between pre-T1D and healthy donors. Naïve CD4⁺ T cells derived from pre-T1D patients displayed 32 dysregulated miRNAs compared with the HC, of which 28 were decreased (Zhang *et al.*, 2016). Multiple miRNAs within the chromosome 14q32 cluster, such as miRNA-342, have been found to be positively regulate the expression of the mRNAs of some auto-Ags (for example, IA-2, IA-2 β and GAD65) in T1D (Abuhatzira *et al.*, 2015). Pancreatic β -cells have distinct miRNA expression patterns that can regulate β -cells development and/or functions. Micro-RNA dysregulation in β -cells induced by proinflammatory cytokines or infiltrating immune cells in islets or OS is implicated in β -cells dysfunction (for example, impaired insulin synthesis or secretion) and cell apoptosis, which contribute to the development of T1D (Zheng *et al.*, 2017).

In 2010, Roggli *et al.*, determined the influences of proinflammatory cytokines on miRNA expression in β -cells and investigated their presumable relationship with β -cells survival and/or functions.

The evaluation of miRNA expression profiles through microarray technology revealed three differentially expressed miRNAs. Specifically, miRNA-21, miRNA-34a, and miRNA-146a expression levels were increased both by IL-1 β and by the cytokine mix of IL-1 β , TNF- α and IFN- γ . Of particular interest, IL-1 β alone was revealed as the strongest inducer of miRNA-21 and miRNA-146a expression, although these miRNAs were also upregulated by TNF- α but not by IFN- γ . The expression of miRNA-34a was equally stimulated by IL-1 β and TNF- α , while IFN- γ did not show any effect on its expression levels. Whereas short exposure to cytokines leads to impaired insulin secretory

machinery, a prolonged cytokine exposure leads to increased apoptotic cell death. Interestingly, it was shown that this phenomenon might be partially mediated by miRNAs. Indeed, a lower cell death rate was observed by blocking miRNA-34a or miRNA-146a activity, while miRNA-21 knockdown did not show such effect and, conversely, promoted apoptosis. These data indicate a role for these miRNAs in cytokine-mediated cell death secondary to prolonged cytokine exposure and established a link between cytokines and miRNAs in β -cells (Ventriglia *et al.*, 2015).

Dicer 1 or argonaute-2 (Ago2) deficiency can affect the valuable formation of overall functional miRNA patterns in pancreatic β -cells. Beta-cell-specific ablation of Dicer 1 can result in the onset of diabetes as a consequence of impaired insulin biosynthesis and glucose-stimulated insulin secretion (Mandelbaum *et al.*, 2012). On the other hand, another study has indicated that Ago2 is also critical for the insulin-secreting capacity and compensatory expansion of β -cells. Deletion of Ago2 in insulin-producing β -cells (the mouse insulinoma β -cells line 6) enhances insulin production (Tattikota *et al.*, 2013).

Thioredoxin-interacting protein (Txnip) is a key regulator of β -cells loss in diabetes. Thioredoxin-interacting protein expression is increased in diabetes and causes β -cells apoptosis, whereas its deficiency is protective against both T1D and T2D. The proapoptotic and diabetogenic functions of Txnip are associated with the Txnip-mediated changes in miRNAs, such as miRNA-204 and miRNA-200 (Filiis *et al.*, 2014). Thioredoxin-interacting protein can induce miRNA-204 expression, which in turn regulates *Mafa* (insulin transcription factors) expression and thus modulates β -cells functions, such as insulin production (Xu *et al.*, 2013). In addition, Txnip impairs β -cells functions by inducing

miRNA-200. Micro-RNA-200 has been demonstrated to target and decrease zinc finger E-box-binding homeobox 1 (Zeb1) and promotes β -cells apoptosis. The miRNA-200-induced inhibition of epithelial-mesenchymal transition is mediated by direct targeting of the E-cadherin transcriptional repressor (Zeb1), resulting in increased expression of the E-cadherin transmembrane protein, strengthening of the cell-cell adherens junctions, and maintenance of the epithelial phenotype (Filius *et al.*, 2014).

Another study showed that IFN- γ increased Txnip expression in β -cells via inhibition of miRNA-17, whereas overexpression of miRNA-17 alleviated the cytokine effect (Hong *et al.*, 2016). Interferon- γ has been reported to lead to miRNA-17 degradation, probably due to the effective activation of inositol-requiring transmembrane kinase/endoribonuclease 1 α (Upton *et al.*, 2012).

Grieco *et al.*, (2017) also reported that miRNA-23a, miRNA-23b and miRNA-149 were downregulated upon exposure of β -cells to the proinflammatory cytokines IL-1 β +IFN- γ . These downregulated miRNAs were further demonstrated to modulate the expression levels of the proapoptotic Bcl2-only proteins Dp5 and Puma, consequently affecting β -cells apoptosis.

Experimental data has shown altered levels of miRNAs within the islets of non-obese diabetic mice during the pre-diabetic phase, and the expression of specific miRNAs was affected when exposing both murine- and human islets to pro-inflammatory cytokines (Roggli *et al.*, 2012).

2.9.5.3 Micro-RNAs Act as Potent Biomarkers for T1D

Over 2500 miRNAs have been described in humans, creating a complex regulatory network since each single miRNA can bind to several different mRNAs. These molecules are expressed to a different degree in

different tissues, and while the majority is found within cells, they can also be detected in serum (Åkerman *et al.*, 2018). Serum miRNAs molecules are highly stable in cell-free body fluids like serum, with high resistance to RNAase digestion and with an ability to remain intact in extreme conditions like low/high pH, boiling, freeze/thaw cycles and extended storage, making them ideal for use in the clinical setting as biomarkers (Chen *et al.*, 2008).

Because miRNAs are expressed broadly in a variety of tissues, none to date can be considered as exclusive to β -cells. However, several miRNAs have been proposed as biomarkers in individuals with T1D (Van *et al.*, 2013).

In-depth sequencing of human islets and isolated β -cells revealed >25 miRNAs that show relative enrichment in β -cells (Van *et al.*, 2013).

Considering their omnipresence, it is likely that miRNAs are involved in the gene regulation related to development of T1D. There are indeed reports on differentially expressed miRNAs in peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) (Yang *et al.*, 2015) and in specific immune cell subsets like Treg cells from T1D patients (Åkerman *et al.*, 2018). Alterations in serum levels have also been observed in newly diagnosed T1D, where some specific miRNAs appear to be related to glycemic control (Samandari *et al.*, 2017).

Micro-RNA-326 expression is significantly increased in PBMCs from T1D patients; the elevated levels correlate with ongoing islet autoimmunity and the disease severity. This miRNA expression is upregulated in Ab-positive T1D patients compared with Ab-negative T1D subjects. The increase in miRNA-326 expression correlates with ongoing islet autoimmunity and may serve as a candidate biomarker for the autoimmune process in T1D (Sebastiani *et al.*, 2011).

Other than a previous report on altered miRNAs expression in CD4⁺ T cell subsets of FDRs of T1D patients was positive for auto-Abs ([Zhang et al., 2016](#)), **data on miRNAs expression during the pre-diabetic period is scarce**. Therefore current study aimed to study whether deviations of miRNAs levels in serum could be detected in children positive for islet auto-Abs, considered at high risk of T1D.

Micro-RNAs in blood cells can be used as potential biomarkers for many autoimmune diseases, including T1D ([Zheng et al., 2017](#)). [Yang et al., \(2015\)](#) identified 26 miRNAs and 1218 genes that were differentially expressed in PBMCs from newly diagnosed T1D patients. Micro-RNA-146 was one of the most downregulated molecules and was linked to ongoing islet autoimmunity in T1D patients. Also, miRNA-21a and miRNA-93 are downregulated in the PBMCs of T1D patients compared with healthy individuals ([Salas-Perez et al., 2013](#)). In addition to controlling gene expression in blood cells, many miRNAs are also detected in serum or plasma and other body fluids (urine, saliva and breast milk) in association with microparticles, such as microvesicles or exosomes, or with proteins. Although the functions of these miRNAs remain obscure, circulating miRNAs can serve as potential biomarkers for the detection of various forms of cancers and autoimmune diseases. The analysis of miRNAs expression patterns in serum, plasma or other body fluids also aids in the development of new approaches for the prediction of T1D ([Zheng et al., 2017](#)).

In a previous study, sera were prospectively obtained from a group of 40 children 1, 3, 6, 12 and 60 months after T1D diagnosis and evaluated for six miRNAs expression (miRNA-24, miRNA-146a, miRNA-194, miRNA-197, miRNA-301a and miRNA-375). Micro-RNA-375 was found highly expressed in islets and is essential for pancreas

development, insulin gene expression and insulin secretion. Its downregulation might serve as a biomarker for β -cells death and the prediction of diabetes (Samandari *et al.*, 2017). Interestingly, one more previous study reported that the serum miRNA-375 level was lower in children with newly diagnosed T1D than in the age-matched control individuals (Marchand *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, it was speculated that a sudden increase in circulating miRNA-375 prior to T1D onset was likely to result from a pool of miRNA-375 immediately released during the process of β -cell death; in turn, this level will decrease after T1D onset, which may reflect β -cells residual functions (Zheng *et al.*, 2017).

2.9.5.4 Micro-RNAs may be Potential Therapeutic Targets for T1D

Abnormal miRNAs expression patterns can lead to the dysfunction of immune responses and insulin secretion. Restoration of miRNAs expression to normal levels may have therapeutic potential for the control of immune homeostasis and the maintenance of sufficient insulin release. The potential of miRNA gene therapy strategies has been tested in several studies. Anti-miRNA oligonucleotides are one of the most common strategies in miRNA gene therapy; in this strategy, anti-miRNA oligonucleotides specifically bind to miRNA molecules and subsequently prevent the binding of miRNAs to their target genes. Other oligonucleotide-based strategies involve miRNA mimics, which have the same nucleotide sequences as endogenous miRNAs. In addition, the regulation of miRNAs by viral based or reagent-based transfection has been successfully applied *in vivo* and *in vitro*, and has exhibited therapeutic potential for T1D (Ventura *et al.*, 2008 and Zheng *et al.*, 2017).

Alternative strategies to targeting miRNAs therapeutically by direct inhibiting Drosha, Dicer or other miRNA pathway components are being

investigated. Conversely, where reduced miRNA expressed is associated with a disease phenotype and increased expression of relevant miRNA could be of potential therapeutic relevance to rescue disease phenotype, introduction of miRNA mimics is being investigated. However, suitable expression vectors have yet to be identified for the safe delivery and maintenance of such effects long-term (Esau and Monia, 2007).

Chapter Three

Materials and Methods

3.1 Study Groups

3.1.1 Patients

Patients were selected from those attending the Diabetes and Endocrinology Specialist Center at Thi-Qar province during the period between May 2018 and November 2018. A total of 35 newly onset T1D patients (17 males and 18 females) with an age range from 10 to 18 years were involved in this study after strict application of the exclusion criteria. Data were collected through direct interview with the patient (a copy of the questionnaire data sheet is provided in appendix I). A written consent was obtained from each patient (or his guardian) participating in this study to fulfill the international research ethical criteria.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with the following criteria were excluded from the current study:

- Patients who had been diagnosed with T1D were more than one year.
- Patients with non-T1D.
- Patients taking corticosteroid therapy for the last 4 weeks.
- Presence of any other autoimmune or chronic disease.
- Recent surgery (during the last 6 months).
- Taking any biological agents.
- Recent blood transfusions (during the last 6 months).
- Presence of any diabetes complications such as nephropathy, neuropathy, and retinopathy.
- Uncontrolled hyperglycemia.
- Absence of FDRs.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients with the following criteria were included in the current study:

- Recent diagnosis of T1D (less than one year).

- The patients have FDRs.
- Absence of any type of diabetes complications.
- Patients with controlled hyperglycemia.
- Have none of the above exclusion criteria.

3.1.2 First Degree Relatives

A total of 35 FDRs (22 males and 13 females) of T1D patients with age range from 4–39 years were involved in this study.

Their exclusion criteria were as follow:

- FDRs taking corticosteroid therapy for the last 4 weeks.
- Presence of any other autoimmune or chronic disease.
- Recent surgery (during the last 6 months).
- Taking any biological agents.
- Recent blood transfusions (during the last 6 months).

3.1.3 Controls

A total of 20 apparently healthy individuals (10 males and 10 females) were included in the study. Their age range was from 5-30 years. The same exclusion criteria of the FDRs group were followed for this group, and in addition, subjects with even a simple infection were also excluded. All subjects of this group have no family history of DM.

3.2 Materials

3.2.1 Equipment and Instruments: as in Table 3.1.

Table (3.1): Equipment and instruments used in this study

Equipment/Instruments	Manufacturing Company	Country
Beakers with different sizes	HBG	Germany
Centrifuge	Fisher Scientific	USA
Cool box	-	China
Cylinders and flask with different sizes	HBG	Germany
Digital timer	-	China
Freezer	Ishtar	Iraq
Incubator	Memmert	Germany

Micropipette with different sizes	Human	Germany
Micro Spin Centrifuge	My Fugene	China
Microtiter Plate Washer	Biokit	Germany
Microtiter Plate Reader	Biokit	Germany
Mic qPCR Cycler	Bio-molecular System	Australia
Multi-channel pipette	Human	Germany
Ordinary Balance	-	China
Quantus Florometer	Promega	USA
Refrigerator	Beko	Turkey
Shaker	KAHN	Japan
Thermal Cycler	BioRad	USA
Vortex Mixer	QLS	England
Water Bath	Histo-line	England
Water Distiller	GallenKamp	England

3.2.2 Disposables: as in Table 3.2.

Table (3.2): Disposable laboratory equipment

Equipment	Manufacturing Company	Country
Cotton	Kardelen	Turkey
Eppendorf tubes with different sizes	Citotest	China
Filter paper	Whatmann	England
Free microtiter plate	Ratiolab	Germany
Gloves	-	Malaysia
Mic tube	Bio-molecular System	Australia
Pipette tips	-	China
Plain tubes	AFNA	Jordan
Syringes	Medeco	Belgium
Vacuum tubes: 5 milliliter (ml)	-	China

3.2.3 Chemicals and Reagents: as in Table 3.3.

Table (3.3): Chemicals and reagents

Materials	Manufacturing Company	Country
Chloroform	Lichrosolv	Germany
Deoxynucleotide triphosphates	Promega	USA
Ethanol (70%)	Romil Pure Chemistry	England
Isopropanol	Romil Pure Chemistry	England
MgCl ₂	Promega	USA
M-MLV-reaction buffer	Promega	USA

M-MLV-reverse transcriptase (RT)	Promega	USA
Nuclease Free Water	Promega	USA
RNasin	Promega	USA
Trizol	Thermo Scientific	USA

M-MLV=moloney murine leukemia virus.

3.2.4 Kits: as in Table 3.4.

Table (3.4): Kits used in this study

Kits	Company	Country
Connecting peptide level	Demeditec	Germany
Glutamic acid decarboxylase auto-Abs level	Demeditec	Germany
GoTaq qPCR master mix	Promega	USA
Human islet antigen-2 antibody	Cusabio	China
Human total antioxidant capacity	Mybiosource	USA
Quantifluor DNA system	Promega	USA

qPCR=quantitative polymerase chain reaction.

3.2.5 Primers: as in Table 3.5 and 3.6 (primers were designed by using primer 3 software).

Table (3.5): Primers for miRNA-25

Primers	Sequence (5'—3')	Company	Country
Reverse transcriptase	GTTGGCTCTGGTG- CAGGGTCCGAGGTATTCGCAC- CAGAGCCAACTCAGAC	Macrogen	South Korea
Forward	GTGCATTGCACTTGTCTCG	Macrogen	South Korea
Reverse	GTGCAGGGTCCGAGGT	Macrogen	South Korea

Table (3.6): Primers for miRNA-375

Primers	Sequence (5'—3')	Company	Country
Reverse transcriptase	GTTGGCTCTGGTG- CAGGGTCCGAGGTATTCG- CACCAGAGCCAACTCACGC	Macrogen	South Korea
Forward	GTGTTTGTTCGTTCCGGCTC	Macrogen	South Korea
Reverse	GTGCAGGGTCCGAGGT	Macrogen	South Korea

3.3 Methods

3.3.1 Study Protocol

The tests procedures were executed in the Diabetes and Endocrinology Specialist Center/Health Department of Thi-Qar, Imam Hussein Teaching Hospital/Health Department of Thi-Qar, and Specialist Laboratory Center/Baghdad (Scheme 3.1).

Scheme (3.1): Study protocol

1. Subject's data collection by written questionnaire through direct interviewing.
2. Serum samples collections.
3. Transportation and storage of samples.
4. Testing serum samples from all study groups for serological findings of the following biomarkers:
 - i. Auto-Abs against pancreatic islet-cells Ags including GAD auto-Abs and IA-2A to be measured by using ELISA.
 - ii. Connecting peptide level to be measured by using ELISA.
 - iii. Total antioxidant capacity to be measured by using ABTS method.
 - iv. Investigating the expression of miRNA-25 and miRNA-375 for their suggested role in T1D by using RT-qPCR.
5. Tabulation of all tests results.
6. Statistical analysis for any correlational inter-relationships of all tested parameters.

3.3.2 Samples Collection and Serum Separation

From each subject; 3-4 ml of peripheral blood was collected by vein puncture. The collected samples were placed in vacuum tube and allowed to clot at room temperature, and then centrifuged at 1500 round per minute (min) (RPM) for 10 min for serum production.

3.3.3 Storage and Transportation of Serum Samples

Each serum sample was divided into several aliquots and stored at -20 centigrade (C°) until needed for serological investigation. One of serum aliquots was mixed with trizol (400 microliter (µl) serum + 600 µl trizol) which is used for RNA extraction. The stored sera were transported in cooling box to Imam Hussein Teaching Hospital/Health Department of Thi-Qar to perform the serological tests, while sera with trizol were

transported in cooling box to Specialist Laboratory center/Baghdad to perform RT-qPCR.

3.3.4 Anti-glutamic Acid Decarboxylase (anti-GAD) Assay

The anti-GAD65 auto-Abs ELISA kit is intended for use by professional persons only, for the quantitative determination of GAD Ab in human serum (Demeditec, Germany).

- **Principle:** In anti-GAD ELISA kit, anti-GAD Ab in patient's sera, calibrators and controls are allowed to interact with GAD65 coated Ag onto ELISA plate wells. After one hour incubation, the samples are discarded leaving anti-GAD Ab bound to the immobilized GAD65 Ag on the plate. GAD65-biotin Ag is added in a second incubation step where, through the ability of anti-GAD Ab in the samples to act divalently, a bridge is formed between GAD65 immobilized Ag on the plate and GAD65-biotin. The amount of GAD65-biotin Ag bound is then determined in a third incubation step by addition of streptavidin peroxidase, which binds specifically to biotin. Excess, unbound streptavidin peroxidase is then washed away and addition of tetra-methylbenzidine (TMB) results in formation of a blue color. This reaction is stopped by the addition of stop solution causing the well contents to turn yellow. The absorbance of the yellow reaction mixture at 450 nanometer (nm) is then read using an ELISA plate reader. A higher absorbance indicates the presence of anti-GAD Ab of the test samples. The measuring interval is 5–2000 unit (U)/ml.

- **Contents of the kit:**

Components/Reagents	Quantity	Volume
GAD65 coated wells	96	-
Calibrator 1	1 vial	0.7 ml (5 U/ml)
Calibrator 2	1 vial	0.7 ml (18 U/ml)
Calibrator 3	1 vial	0.7 ml (35 U/ml)
Calibrator 4	1 vial	0.7 ml (120 U/ml)

Calibrator 5	1 vial	0.7 ml (250 U/ml)
Calibrator 6	1 vial	0.7 ml (2000 U/ml)
Positive control	1 vial	0.7 ml
Negative control	1 vial	0.7 ml
GAD65-biotin	3 vial	Lyophilized
Reconstitution buffer for GAD65-biotin	2 vial	15 ml
Streptavidin peroxidase	1 vial	0.7 ml (concentrated)
Diluent for streptavidin peroxidase	1 vial	15 ml
Peroxidase substrate	1 vial	15 ml
Concentrated wash solution	1 vial	125 ml (10 x)
Stop solution	1 vial	12 ml
Instruction manual	1	-

- **Sensitivity and specificity:** Clinical sensitivity: 92% and clinical specificity: 98%.
- **Reagents preparation:** All reagents were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.
- **Samples preparation:** All samples were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.
- **Assay procedure:** The assay procedure was followed according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.
- **Calculation of results:** A calibration curve was established by plotting calibrator concentration on the X-axis against the absorbance of the calibrators on the Y-axis. The GAD Ab concentrations in patient's sera were read off the calibration curve (Figure 3.2).

Figure (3.2): Glutamic acid decarboxylase-65 auto-antibody standard curve

▪ **Interpretation of results:**

U/ml	Interpretation
<5	Negative
≥5	Positive

3.3.5 Human Islet Antigen-2 Antibody Assay

- **Principle:** This assay employs the indirect qualitative enzyme immunoassay technique. The microtiter plate provided in this kit has been pre-coated with Ag. Samples are pipetted into the wells with anti-human Ig conjugated horseradish peroxidase (HRP). Any Abs specific for the Ag present will bind to the pre-coated Ag. Following a wash to remove any unbound reagent, a substrate solution is added to the wells and color develops in proportion to the amount of human IA-2A bound in the initial step. The color development is stopped and the intensity of the color is measured (Cusabio, China).
- **Contents of the kit:**

Components/Reagents	Quantity	Volume (ml)
Coated assay plate	1 (96 wells)	-
Negative control	1 vial	1

Positive control	1 vial	1
Sample diluent	1 vial	20
HRP-conjugate	1 vial	10
Wash buffer	1 vial	20 (25 x concentrate)
Substrate A	1 vial	5
Substrate B	1 vial	5
Stop solution	1 vial	5
Adhesive strip (for 96 wells)	4	-
Instruction manual	1	-

- **Specificity and sensitivity:** This assay has high sensitivity and excellent specificity for the detection of human IA-2A. No significant cross-reactivity or interference between human IA-2A and analogues was observed.
- **Reagents preparation:** All reagents were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.
- **Samples preparation:** All samples were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.
- **Assay procedure:** The assay procedure was followed according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.
- **Calculation of results:**
 - $OD_{\text{sample}} / OD_{\text{negative control}} \geq 2.5$: positive
 - $OD_{\text{sample}} / OD_{\text{negative control}} < 2.5$: negative

Where: OD= optical density

3.3.6 Connecting Peptide Level Assay

- **Principle:** The C-peptide kit is a solid phase ELISA, based on the principle of competitive binding. The microtiter wells are coated with anti-mouse Abs, which binds a monoclonal Ab directed towards a unique antigenic site on the C-peptide molecule. Endogenous C-peptide of a patient sample competes with a C-peptide-HRP conjugate for binding to the coated Ab. After incubation the unbound conjugate is washed off. The amount of bound peroxidase conjugate is inversely

proportional to the concentration of C-peptide in the sample. After addition of the substrate solution, the intensity of color developed is inversely proportional to the concentration of C-peptide in the patient sample (Demeditec, Germany).

▪ **Contents of the kit:**

Components/Reagents	Quantity	Volume
Microtiter wells coated with anti-mouse-Ab	96	-
Standard 0	1 vial	Lyophilized (0.0 ng/ml)
Standard 1	1 vial	Lyophilized (0.2 ng/ml)
Standard 2	1 vial	Lyophilized (0.7 ng/ml)
Standard 3	1 vial	Lyophilized (2.0 ng/ml)
Standard 4	1 vial	Lyophilized (6.0 ng/ml)
Standard 5	1 vial	Lyophilized (16.0 ng/ml)
Sample diluent	1 vial	3 ml
Antiserum	1 vial	7 ml
Enzyme conjugate	1 vial	14 ml
Enzyme complex	1 vial	14 ml
Substrate solution	1 vial	14 ml
Stop solution	1 vial	14 ml
Wash solution	1 vial	30 ml (40 x)
Instruction manual	1	-

ng=nanogram.

- **Specificity:** The cross-reactivity of intact or split-proinsulin is clinically not significant.
- **Sensitivity:** The analytical sensitivity of the C-peptide ELISA was calculated by subtracting 2 standard deviations (SD) from the mean of 20 replicate analyses of the zero standards and was found to be 0.064 nanogram (ng)/ml.
- **Reagents preparation:** All reagents were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.
- **Samples preparation:** All samples were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.
- **Assay procedure:** The assay procedure was followed according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

- **Calculation of results:** A standard curve was established by plotting the absorbance obtained from each standard against its concentration with absorbance value on vertical (Y) axis and concentration on the horizontal (X) axis. By using the absorbance value for each sample the corresponding concentration was determined from the standard curve (Figure 3.3).

Figure (3.3): Connecting peptide standard curve

3.3.7 Total Antioxidant Capacity Assay

- **Principle:** The principle of the ABTS method for determining the TAC is as follows. ABTS is oxidized to green $ABTS^+$ by appropriate oxidant, which can be inhibited if antioxidants exist. The TAC of the sample can be determined and calculated by measuring the absorbance of $ABTS^+$ at 405 nm. Trolox is an analog of vitamin E and has a similar antioxidant capacity to that of vitamin E. Trolox is used as a reference for other antioxidant. For example, the TAC of Trolox is 1, and then the antioxidant capacity of the other substance with the same concentration is showed by the ratio of its antioxidant capacity to Trolox antioxidant capacity (Mybiosource, USA).

- **Kit components:**

Components/Reagents	Quantity	Volume
Detection buffer	1 vial	20 ml
ABTS solution	1 vial	1 ml
Peroxide solution	1 vial	0.5 ml
Peroxidase	1 vial	0.2 ml
Trolox solution	1 vial	0.1 ml (10 millimolar (mM))

- **Reagents preparation:** All reagents were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions. Dilution of Trolox solution was prepared using 10 mM Trolox solution as it is shown in Table 3.7.

Table (3.7): Total antioxidant capacity Trolox standard solution dilution

Trolox solution 10 mM	Dilution
1.0 mM	10 μ l Trolox (10 mM) + 90 μ l distilled water
0.8 mM	80 μ l Trolox (1.0 mM) + 20 μ l distilled water
0.4 mM	50 μ l Trolox (0.8 mM) + 50 μ l distilled water
0.2 mM	50 μ l Trolox (0.4 mM) + 50 μ l distilled water
0.1 mM	50 μ l Trolox (0.2 mM) + 50 μ l distilled water

- **Samples preparation:** All samples were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.
- **Assay procedure:** The assay procedure was followed according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.
- **Calculation of results:** According to standards concentrations and corresponding OD values, the linear regression equation of the standard curve was calculated (the OD on Y-axis and concentration on X-axis). Then according to the OD value of samples, the concentrations of the corresponding samples were calculated from standard curve (Figure 3.4).

Figure (3.4): Total antioxidant capacity standard curve

- **Assay range:** 0.5-2 mM for serum and plasma, and 0.2-3 mM for urine.

3.3.8 Reverse Transcriptase qPCR

- **Principle:** Reverse transcriptase is an approach for converting and amplifying a single-stranded RNA template to yield abundant double-stranded DNA product. In the RT step, RT synthesizes single-stranded complementary DNA (cDNA) molecules, which is complementary to the RNA template. This is termed first strand synthesis. In the PCR step, during the first round of the thermal cycle, a thermostable DNA Pol synthesizes single-stranded DNA molecules complementary to the cDNA molecules, thus generating double-stranded DNA template. This is termed second strand synthesis. During subsequent rounds of the thermal cycle, the DNA Pol exponentially amplifies the double-stranded DNA template.

- **RNA isolation and purification:** RNA purification was according to Trizol reagent method as follow:
 1. For sample lysis; 400 μ l of serum was added to Eppendorf containing 600 μ l of Trizol reagent, the lysate was homogenized by pipetting up and down several times.
 2. For three phases separation, 200 μ l of chloroform was added to the lysate, then the tube cap secured.
 3. All mixtures were incubated for 2–3 min at room temperature, and then centrifuged for 10 min at 12000 RPM. The mixture was then separated into a lower organic phase, interphase, and a colorless upper aqueous phase.
 4. The aqueous upper layer containing the RNA was transferred to a new Eppendorf tube and 500 μ l of isopropanol was added (for RNA precipitation).
 5. The Eppendorf tube was incubated for 10 min at 2-8 C°, and then centrifuged at 12000 RPM for 10 min.
 6. After this step, total RNA was formed as a white gel-like pellet at the bottom of Eppendorf tube.
 7. Supernatant was discarded.
 8. For RNA washing, 500 μ l of 70% ethanol was added and vortex briefly.
 9. The Eppendorf tube was centrifuged at 10000 RPM for 5 min.
 10. Supernatant was carefully aspirated and left the pellet for drying in air.
 11. For RNA solubility, pellet was rehydrated in 50 μ l of nuclease free water (NFW) and then incubated in a water bath (55-60 C°) for 10-15 min.

3.3.8.1 Complementary DNA Synthesis

- **Reverse transcriptase primers preparation:**

1. Lyophilized primers were dissolved by adding 240 μl of NFW into each primers vial (the concentration was 100 micromolar (μM)).
2. Each vial was vortexed for 5 second and then span in a micro-centrifuge for 5 second.
3. A volume of 10 μM of primers (stock solution) was prepared after adding 10 μl of 100 μM primer solution into Eppendorf tube containing 90 μl of NFW.
4. The step 2 was repeated.

- **Reverse transcriptase step:**

Components	Stock Conc.	Working Conc.	Volume	
			1 sample	50.05 samples
dNTPs	10 mM	1 mM	0.1 μl	5.005 μl
M-MLV-RT	200 u/ μl	20 u/ μl	0.1 μl	5.005 μl
M-MLV Reaction Buffer	5 x	0.05 x	2 μl	100.1 μl
RNasin	40 u/ μl	4 u/ μl	0.15 μl	7.5075 μl
Nuclease Free Water	-	-	2.65 μl	132.6325 μl
RT primer	10 μM	2 μM	2 μl	100.1 μl
Master mix			7 μl	350.35 μl
Two master mix were prepared one contain RT primer for miRNA-25 and the other contain RT primer for miRNA-375.				
RNA (sample)	-	-	3 μl	
Total volume	-	-	10 μl	
Aliquot per single run	7 μl of master mix was mixed with 3 μl of template RNA sample.			
Thermal Cycler Program				
Step	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Time	Cycle	
Annealing	16	30 min	1	
Extension	42	30 min		
Enzyme inactivation	85	5 min		
Hold	4	10 min		

Conc=concentration, dNTPs=deoxynucleotide triphosphates and M-MLV-RT=moloney murine leukemia virus reverse transcriptase.

- **Determination of cDNA concentration:** Quantus fluorometer was used to detect the concentration of cDNA in order to detect the quality

of samples for downstream applications. For 1 μl of cDNA, 199 μl of diluted quantifluor dye were mixed. After 5 min of incubation at room temperature in dark place, cDNA concentration values were determined. Diluted quantifluor dye was prepared after mixing 1 μl of quantifluor dye with 199 μl of 1 x tris-EDTA (TE) buffer.

3.3.8.2 Real Time PCR

- **Forward and universal reverse primers preparation:** A volume of 10 μM of primers (stock solution) was prepared by using the same procedure mentioned above of RT primers preparation.
- **GoTaq qPCR master mix components:**

Components
dNTPs
Thermus aquaticus polymerase
MgCl ₂
Sybr green
Reaction buffer

- **Real time PCR step:** as in Figures 3.5 and 3.6, and appendices II and IV.

Components	Stock Conc.	Working Conc.	Volume	
			1 sample	50.05 samples
qPCR master Mix	2 x	1x	5 μl	250.25 μl
MgCl ₂	25 mM	0.625 mM	0.25 μl	12.5125 μl
Forward primer	10 μM	1 μM	0.5 μl	25.025 μl
Reverse primer	10 μM	1 μM	0.5 μl	25.025 μl
Nuclease Free Water	-	-	2.75	137.6375 μl
Master mix			9 μl	450.45 μl
Two master mix were prepared one contain forward and reverse primers for miRNA-25 and the other contain primers for miRNA-375.				
cDNA	-	-	1 μl	
Total volume			10 μl	
Aliquot per single run	9 μl of master mix was mixed with 1 μl of template cDNA sample.			
Real Time PCR Program				
Step	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Time	Cycles	
Initial Denaturation	95	5 min	1	
Denaturation	95	15 second		

Annealing	60	15 second	40
Extension	72	15 second	

Conc=concentration.

Figure (3.5): Real time polymerase chain reaction step of miRNA-25

Figure (3.6): Real time polymerase chain reaction step of miRNA-375

3.3.8.3 Gene Expression Calculation (Chen *et al.*, 2005, Varkonyi-Gasic *et al.*, 2007 and Stephenson, 2010)

$$m = (n \text{ bp}) \times (1.096 \times 10^{-21} \text{ g/bp})$$

Where: m= mass.

n=DNA size (bp).

$$m = 50 \text{ bp} \times 1.096 \times 10^{-21} \text{ g/bp}$$

$$m = 54.8 \times 10^{-21} \text{ g.}$$

$$m \text{ (ng)} = m \text{ (g)} \times 10^9 \text{ ng}$$

$$m \text{ (ng)} = 54.8 \times 10^{-21} \text{ g} \times 10^9 \text{ ng}$$

$$m = 54.8 \times 10^{-12} \text{ ng}$$

Copy number = cDNA concentration (ng/μl)/m (ng).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Copy number (miRNA-25)} &= 10 \text{ ng}/\mu\text{l} / 54.8 \times 10^{-12} \text{ ng} \\ &= 18 \times 10^{10} \text{ per } \mu\text{l}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Copy number (miRNA-375)} &= 8 \text{ ng}/\mu\text{l} / 54.8 \times 10^{-12} \text{ ng} \\ &= 15 \times 10^{10} \text{ per } \mu\text{l}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Where: bp=base pair, g=gram and ng=nanogram.

3.3.8.4 Absolute Quantification by the Standard Curve

The standard curve method employed a series dilution of known template copy number in the qPCR assay (please read gene expression calculation). Linear regression of log concentration (copy/μl⁻¹) versus threshold cycle (C_T) gives the standard curve, and this is then used to calculate template concentration (copy/μl⁻¹) of the samples (Figures 3.8 and 3.10).

- **Standard curve of miRNA-25:** Four of 200 μl tubes were prepared, 18 μl of NFW was added to each tube and then 2 μl from the sample of 18 X 10¹⁰ copy/μl⁻¹ was added to the first tube and made a serial dilution by transferred 2 μl from first tube to second tube and so on.

The standard curve reaction started from the tube of 18 X 10⁸ copy/μl⁻¹ to the tube of 18 X 10⁶ copy/μl⁻¹ (Figure 3.7 and appendix III).

Figure (3.7): Real time polymerase chain reaction step of miRNA-25 standard curve samples

Figure (3.8): Micro-RNA-25 standard curve

- Standard Curve of miRNA-375:** Three of 200 μ l tubes were prepared, 18 μ l of NFW was added to each tube and then 2 μ l from sample of 15×10^{10} copy/ μ l⁻¹ was added to the first tube and made a serial dilution by transferred 2 μ l from first tube to second tube and so on.

The standard curve reaction started from the tube of 15×10^9 copy/ μl^{-1} to the tube of 15×10^7 copy/ μl^{-1} (Figure 3.9 and appendix V).

Figure (3.9): Real time polymerase chain reaction step of miRNA-375 standard curve samples

Figure (3.10): Micro-RNA-375 standard curve

3.3.9 Tabulation of the Results

Results tabulation was performed using, Microsoft Office Word 2010 and Microsoft Office Excel 2010 programs.

3.3.10 Statistical Analyses

For data presentation and analysis, statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 24 was used. Descriptive statistics included; the use of frequencies, relative frequencies, means, and SD. Chi-Square statistical test, simple correlation (r) and simple linear regression were used to test for associations between variables. The differences being considered as statistically significant when the P-value was <0.05 .

Chapter Four

Results and Discussion

4.1 Study Groups

Table 4.1 demonstrates the group classification of this study enrolled subjects. Thirty five T1D patients (17 males and 18 females) and thirty five of their FDRs (22 males and 13 females) attending the Diabetes and Endocrinology Specialist Center at Thi-Qar province during the period between May 2018 and November 2018, with age range of 10-18 years and 4-39 years, respectively, and twenty apparently healthy individuals (10 males and 10 females) with age range of 5-30 years were involved in this study after strict application of the exclusion criteria.

Table (4.1): Classification of the study groups

Total Subjects (n=90)		
Type 1 Diabetic (T1D)	First Degree Relatives (FDRs)	Healthy Control (HC)
n=35	n=35	n=20

n=number.

4.2 Family History and Endogamy

Family history and endogamy in T1D patients are shown in Figure 4.1. The frequency (FR) of family history and endogamy were 57.1% for both. The differences in the frequencies for both variables were not significant.

Figure (4.1): Distribution of type 1 diabetes patients according to family history and endogamy

The above figure show that the incidence of T1D did not alter in the presence or absence of family history of diabetes and endogamy. Alhonen *et al.*, (2011) was found the T1D or other autoimmune diseases not only

cluster among the parents and siblings of the children case but also occur more often among relatives outside the nuclear family which come in consistent with this study. However, in our opinion the major limitation of the current study was that family history data were based on interviews only and may therefore be inaccurate. Another study (Šipetić *et al.*, 2002) revealed no differences in the occurrence of T1D between the affected and control families, which are in line with current data.

4.3 Autoantibodies

Figure 4.2 shows the anti-GAD Abs results among all study groups. Anti-GAD Abs positive frequency was highest in T1D group (88.6%), followed by FDRs group (11.4%) with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$). Healthy control group was the lowest (5%) with significant difference ($p < 0.05$) compared to T1D group and no significant difference compared to FDRs group. For mean titer, T1D patients exhibited a significant ($p < 0.05$) elevated mean titer (711.5 U/ml) in comparison with FDRs group (59.3 U/ml) and HC group (1.9 U/ml). The difference between FDRs group and healthy control (HC) group was not significant.

Figure (4.2): The results of frequency (%) and mean titer of anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody in all study groups

Islet antigen-2 Abs results in all study groups are shown in Figure 4.3. The IA-2 Abs positivity was with significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher frequency among T1D group (40%) than FDRs group (11.4%) and HC group (5%). The frequency difference for IA-2 Abs positivity between the FDRs group and HC group was not significant.

Figure (4.3): The results of frequency (%) of islet antigen-2 antibody in all study groups

Type 1 diabetes is a chronic inflammatory and multifactorial disease caused by a selective destruction of the insulin producing β -cells in the islets of Langerhans. One theory regarding the causes of T1D is the destruction of pancreatic β -cells due to a defect in immune regulation by infectious or environmental factors that stimulate the immune system in genetically susceptible subjects to develop an autoimmune response against altered pancreatic β -cells Ags. Autoimmunity is regarded as a major factor in the pathophysiology of T1D (Mahdi *et al.*, 2015). Type 1 diabetes is associated with the incidence of humoral and cellular islet autoimmunity, and a defective immune regulation appears to be involved (Mathis and Benoist, 2004). In agreement with these findings the results of this study exhibited a significant elevation of anti-GAD Abs mean titer and IA-2A positivity among T1D patients compared to FDRs and HC groups.

The present study found highest percentage of anti-GAD Abs positivity and IA-2A positivity (88.6% and 40%, respectively) among newly onset T1D patients. This result is in consistent with 67.5% and 33.3%,

respectively, of the same biomarkers as estimated by Mahdi *et al.*, (2015). The above findings point out the important role of islet cells autoimmunity in the pathogenesis of T1D. However, our results seem to be higher than that reported by Damanhoury *et al.*, (2005) in a Saudi Arabian study on individuals with T1D, who reported a frequency % of positivity 54% and 27% for GADA and IA-2A, respectively. Also, in another study from Taiwan, patients with T1D were 47% for GADA positive frequency % and 23% for IA-2A positive frequency % in their sera (Chang *et al.*, 2004). One more important observation is the specificity of the existence of a single auto-Abs which ranged from 92%–99% (Herold *et al.*, 2009) or 85% (Seyfert-Margolis *et al.*, 2006). However, the sensitivity of the existence of a single auto-Abs was as low as 59%–67% (Herold *et al.*, 2009). In another study, it was noticed that the coexistence of both GADA and IA-2A auto-Abs would significantly improve the sensitivity and specificity (Lebastchi and Herold, 2012).

Furthermore the low frequency % of GADA and IA-2A positivity among healthy individuals (1-2% for both) had been found in other studies (Yoon and Jun, 2005, and Calderon and Sacks, 2014) which come in parallel with the current study which exhibited a lower incidence of these auto-Abs (5% for both) in HC group. The reason for such differences in the incidence of such auto-Abs may be due to differences in tests used, technique sensitivity, and difference in patient's genetic makeup and environmental properties.

Many studies revealed that the presence of islet cells auto-Abs, which is considered as immunological biomarkers for the autoimmunity of the T1D, will predict the development of diabetes in the relatives (Regnell and Lernmark, 2017). In respect to this study results, modest frequency % of GADA and IA-2A positivity were observed within FDRs groups

(11.4% for both). The appearance of β -cells auto-Abs is regarded as the earliest established sign of autoimmunity directed against the pancreatic islet β -cells (Couper *et al.*, 2014). Previous studies showed that testing positive for a single auto-Ab was associated with a greater cumulative disease risk in FDRs compared to the general population. Any individuals with double positive auto-Abs are at markedly high risk of developing T1D (Knip *et al.*, 2010). The findings of the current study concluded that the FDRs individual with positive islets auto-Abs may develop T1D during the next years of their life. These auto-Abs may represent one of the early biomarkers for β -cells stress and/or death in the prodromal stages of ongoing T1D proceeding.

4.4 Connecting Peptide

Figure 4.4 shows that the vast majority of T1D patients were below normal level for serum C-peptide (65.7%) compared to FDRs (8.6%) and HC (5%) with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) (no significant difference was recorded between FDRs and HC groups). Concerning the mean titers of C-peptide (Figure 4.4), the lowest was in the T1D group (2.6 ng/ml) compared to the FDRs (5.3 ng/ml) and HC (6.5 ng/ml) with significant differences ($p < 0.05$). The difference in mean titers between FDRs and HC groups was also significant ($p < 0.05$).

Figure (4.4): The results of frequency (%) and mean titer of connecting peptide in all study groups

The use of C-peptide has arisen as a mean to directly evaluate β -cells destruction by autoimmune processes (Lebastchi and Herold, 2012) and it is well known to fulfill an important function in the synthesis of insulin (Wahren *et al.*, 2012). Connecting peptide levels are good indicators of insulin levels in the blood and pancreatic β -cells function (Shetty *et al.*, 2017). The present study reported a significant decrease in C-peptide level in T1D group compared to other study groups, a result with high consistency with the above mentioned studies.

Very few previous studies had prospectively elucidated the changes in C-peptide levels from pre-diabetes, to diagnostic diabetes, and in the years following until C-peptide level are no longer detectable. Studies by Tsai *et al.*, (2006) and Sosenko *et al.*, (2008) have determined a progressive decline in C-peptide level that was relatively minor during the pre-diabetic period compared with the huge changes after diagnosis with hyperglycemia. In consistent with these findings, this study results showed a significant decrease in C-peptide level in T1D patient compared

to pre-diabetes FDRs group and a significant decrease in C-peptide value in the former group compared to HC group. Interpretation of the fluctuation in C-peptide level may be more sophisticated in children due to the age-related increase in C-peptide levels and thus, the absence of an increase may be equivalent to a decline in level (Sosenko *et al.*, 2008).

4.5 Total Antioxidant Capacity

In Figure 4.5, the frequency of TAC below normal level was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) among the members of the T1D group (85.7%) when compared to the FDRs group (65.7%) and HC group (60%). No significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were found between FDRs group and HC group. Figure 4.5 also demonstrated the mean titers of TAC which exhibited a decreased level among T1D group subjects (0.42 mM) compared to an elevated level among the subjects of FDRs group (0.48 mM) and HC group (0.46 mM). The only significant difference was between the T1D and FDRs groups ($p < 0.05$), whereas all other differences between study groups were not significant ($p > 0.05$).

Figure (4.5): The results of frequency (%) and mean titer of total antioxidant capacity in all study groups

The activities of antioxidant enzymes were found to be declined in patients with T1D and in latent autoimmune diabetes patients. The depletion was worse in patients with bad diabetic control (Varvarovská *et al.*, 2004). In the present study, the TAC in patients suffering from T1D was significantly lower than that in the control group as in some other studies (Hisalkar *et al.*, 2012 and Mahdi *et al.*, 2015). In patients with diabetes, the autoxidation of glucose results in the generation of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), this inhibits antioxidant enzymes (Mahdi *et al.*, 2015). Accordingly, the aggregation of H_2O_2 may be one of the explanations for depleted TAC in these patients.

Hyperglycemia, a hallmark of diabetic disease, declines natural antioxidants and promotes the generation of ROS, which has the power to react with all biological components like lipids, proteins, carbohydrates, and DNA and produce cytotoxic actions on cellular activities (Dincer *et al.*, 2002). Hyperglycemia is involved in OS by virtue of the fact that monosaccharides and glycolytic intermediates can produce oxidative reactants (Mahdi *et al.*, 2015). A current study revealed a significant fall in TAC levels, which could be due to increased OS. A decrease in TAC levels can result in an increase of ROS and intensification of lipid peroxidation processes in diabetes (Mahdi *et al.*, 2015).

The results of the current study (Figure 4.5) confirmed the evidence of impaired antioxidative defense in T1D patients in accordance with other studies (Varvarovská *et al.*, 2004) and similar tendency of low antioxidative protection in FDRs of T1D patients. Similar results were recorded by Kural *et al.*, (2011) and speculate that OS may play an important role in pathogenesis of T1D.

4.6 Micro-RNAs

4.6.1 Micro-RNA-25

Regarding serum miRNA-25 in this study, most of the T1D and FDRs subjects (90% and 75%, respectively) were with a depleted level (Figure 4.6) compared to the HC (30%) with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$). However, no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were noticed between T1D group and FDRs group for this parameter. The mean titer for serum miRNA-25 was lowest in the T1D group (1.1×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1}) compared to FDRs (1.6×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1}) and HC groups (3.5×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1}) with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between T1D patients and HC groups (Figure 4.6). However, no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was observed between FDRs group in comparison to T1D and HC groups.

Figure (4.6): The results of frequency (%) and mean titer of miRNA-25 in all study groups

Circulating biomarkers for T1D based on specific auto-Abs measurements which are the most reliable biomarkers in the prodromal phase of T1D, since their appearance typically precedes overt T1D onset for years or even decades (Wenzlau and Hutton, 2013). However, the

predictive value of these biomarkers on the time occurrence of T1D and the degree of death/stress of pancreatic β -cells may go at the expense of the diagnostic sensitivity, as they detect only about 30% of prediabetic relatives (Truyen *et al.*, 2005). Therefore, there is a current need for additional biological markers of higher sensitivity capable of identifying more prediabetic relatives. Micro-RNAs are known to play a central role in posttranscriptional gene regulation and are involved in many cellular processes, such as differentiation, proliferation, and apoptosis. Micro-RNAs are detectable in cell-free circulation, that is, plasma and serum, and thus have been investigated as non-invasive biomarkers in several diseases and pathologic processes (Bushati and Cohen, 2007). The results of this study (Figure 4.6) expressed a significant decrease in miRNA-25 level in T1D group in comparison to HC group. Coinciding with these findings previous studies exhibited a lower miRNA-25 expression in T1D patients (Åkerman *et al.*, 2018). Data on miRNAs expression during the prediabetic period is scarce. Our results revealed a significant decrease in the expression of miRNA-25 among members of FDRs group compared to HC groups. These findings suggests that miRNA-25 is an important disease diagnostic and predictor biomarker.

4.6.2 Micro-RNA-375

The results of serum miRNA-375 are demonstrated in Figure 4.7. The frequency % of lower level serum miRNA-375 was higher in T1D group 7/20 (35%) compared to FDRs 2/20 (10%) and HC 0/10 (0%) groups. These differences were significant ($p < 0.05$) when comparing between T1D and HC groups, but not significant ($p > 0.05$) when comparing between FDRs group and T1D or HC groups. For the mean titer, the FDRs group exhibited the highest mean titer (550×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1}) in comparison with the HC group (435×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1}) with significant

differences ($p < 0.05$). No significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were detected in the miRNA-375 mean titer between the T1D ($488 \times 10^6 \text{ copy}/\mu\text{l}^{-1}$) group and FDRs or HC groups.

Figure (4.7): The results of frequency (%) and mean titer of miRNA-375 in all study groups

Micro-RNA-375 is highly expressed in islets of Langerhans and is essential for pancreas development, insulin gene expression and insulin secretion. Micro-RNA-375 can serve as a biomarker for the detection of β -cells death and the prediction of diabetes (Erener *et al.*, 2013). In this study (Figure 4.7), it has been found that miRNA-375 level is significantly decreased in the serum of T1D group compared to HC group. These data are in agreement with another study which showed that the serum miRNA-375 level was lower in children with newly diagnosed T1D than in the age-matched control individuals (Marchand *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, circulating miRNA-375 level is markedly increased prior to the occurrence of hyperglycemia or 2 weeks before the diabetes onset (Miao *et al.*, 2018). In compatibility with these findings, this study results exhibited a significant elevation of miRNA-375 level among pre-diabetic

FDRs groups in comparison to HC group. Therefore, it is speculated that a sudden increase in circulating miRNA-375 prior to T1D onset was likely a result of a pool of miRNA-375 immediately released during the process of β -cells death; in turn, this level will decrease after T1D onset, which may reflect β -cells residual functions.

4.7 Sensitivity and Specificity of Study Biomarkers

Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) of all study biomarkers in reference to C-peptide test (as gold standard test) (Hope *et al.*, 2016) are calculated according to (Habib *et al.*, 2015) as in Table 4.2. The highest sensitivity was recorded with miRNA-25 and anti-GAD Abs (94.7% and 87%, respectively), followed by TAC (78.3%). The lowest sensitivity was recorded with IA-2A (52.2%). Micro-RNA-25 and IA-2A were the highest in specificity (100% and 83.3%, respectively), whereas the TAC and anti-GAD Abs were the lowest in specificity (0% and 8.3%, respectively). Regarding the PPV of miRNA-25, IA-2A, anti-GAD Abs and TAC biomarkers, the results were 100%, 85.7%, 64.5%, and 60%, respectively. Negative predictive value of the current study biomarkers was higher for miRNA-25 (50%), followed by IA-2A and anti-GAD Abs (47.6% and 25%, respectively), while the NPV of TAC was 0%. For serum miRNA-375, sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV were calculated according the disease duration, because the level of this biomarker is affected by that. Type 1 diabetes patients were divided into groups, the first one with disease duration <6 months (m), while the other with disease duration ≥ 6 -<12 m. Regarding to serum miRNA-375 (<6 m), sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV were 85.7%, 50%, 85.7% and 50%, respectively, while miRNA-375 (≥ 6 -<12 m) were 41.6%, 50%, 83.3%, and 12.5%, respectively.

Table (4.2): The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value of all study biomarkers

Tests		Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV
Anti-GAD		87%	8.3%	64.5%	25%
IA-2A		52.2%	83.3%	85.7%	47.6%
TAC		78.3%	0%	60%	0%
MiRNA-25		94.7%	100%	100%	50%
MiRNA-375	DD (<6 m)	85.7%	50%	85.7%	50%
	DD (≥6 -<12 m)	41.6%	50%	83.3%	12.5%

DD=disease duration, PPV=positive predictive value, NPV=negative predictive value, GAD=glutamic acid decarboxylase, IA-2A=islet antigen-2 antibody and TAC=total antioxidant capacity.

Type 1 Diabetes is characterized by the presence of specific circulating auto-Abs, including; GADA, IA-2A, IAA, ZnT8 and auto-Abs directed against cytoplasmic components of islet cells. Measuring of such auto-Abs is highly important in the diagnosis of T1D and prediction of T1D on patient's relatives, especially in the first-degree family ties (Delic-Sarac *et al.*, 2016). This was true in this study results (Table 4.2) which revealed higher sensitivity (87%) of GADA in diagnosis of T1D and in compatibility with Graham *et al.*, (2002) investigation who reported a higher diagnostic sensitivity of GADA (70%-80%). In the same above table, there was a lower GADA diagnostic specificity (8.3%). Regarding to GADA specificity, both GAD enzyme isoforms; GAD65 and GAD67 are expressed at high concentrations predominantly in the central and peripheral nervous system of mammals, and are localized in the presynaptic terminals of GABAergic inhibitory synapses. A significant amount corresponding to that in the nervous tissue is expressed only in the pancreas, fallopian tubes, and testes. In pancreatic islets, a strong species-specific variation in the expression of the two isoforms of GAD has been described. In human islet β -cells only GAD65 is expressed at high levels (Krueger *et al.*, 2007). These findings concluded that the GAD enzyme is not only expressed by islets β -cells. In respect to these findings, the present study reported lower diagnostic

specificity of GADA. Concerning to the role of IA-2A in the diagnosis and prediction of T1D, the current results showed higher diagnostic specificity (83.3%) and moderate sensitivity (52.2%) of IA-2A in detection of T1D. These results come in consistency with another study (Delic-Sarac *et al.*, 2016) which found the sensitivity of 57% and specificity of 99% for IA-2A in T1D patients.

Previous evidences suggested that OS may play an important role in the etiology of diabetes and diabetic complications. In healthy individuals, oxidative damage to tissues is prevented by a system of defenses that include antioxidant enzymes and small molecules, such as antioxidant vitamins, with scavenging ability (Mahdi *et al.*, 2015). In patients with diabetes, an altered balance between the production of ROS and antioxidant levels has been reported (Sözmen *et al.*, 2001). In agreement with the above cited studies, serum TAC exhibited a high diagnostic sensitivity (78.3%). Oxidative stress contributes to many pathological conditions, including cancer, neurological disorders, atherosclerosis, hypertension, ischemia/perfusion, diabetes, acute respiratory distress syndrome, idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and asthma (Birben *et al.*, 2012). In this study TAC exhibited no diagnostic specificity (0%) of this parameter.

A previous report found an association between miRNA-25 and better glycemic control and residual β -cells function, suggesting a role of miRNA-25 on cell proliferation of the endocrine cells of the pancreas (Nielsen *et al.*, 2012). Consistent with this report, miRNA-25 showed a higher diagnostic sensitivity (94.7%) and specificity (100%) in our study. This study provides suggestive evidence for the role of miRNAs as clinical applicable biomarkers in T1D. The association of miRNA-25 with improved glycaemic control and better residual β -cells function may

indicate that this miRNA could be an important biomarker that could be used during early and intensive management of newly diagnosed diabetes to improve blood glucose control and reduce microvascular complications. These findings should be confirmed in an independent study population; however, we are currently investigating the miRNA-25 levels in all patients from our study cohorts at different time points during disease progression. This study can serve as model for conceptualising the use of miRNAs as clinical relevant biomarkers in which they potentially will be used as beneficial predictors to evaluate clinically meaningful changes in intervention therapies designed to preserve/regenerate β -cells function in new onset T1D.

In destructed β -cells, it is sufficient to detect higher level of miRNA-375 in the blood, and this finding has been supported by increased miRNA-375 in the circulation of newly onset T1D patients but not mature onset diabetes of young subjects. Importantly, the small contribution of β -cells to circulating miR-375 makes this miRNA a diagnostic biomarker for β -cells function and acute-cell death during the T1D development (Latreille *et al.*, 2015). In agreement with the last mentioned study, the results of the current study exhibited a good sensitivity (85.7%) and moderate specificity (50%) of miRNA-375 in the diagnosis of new onset (<6 m) T1D individuals, however, the sensitivity of this biomarkers decreased (41.6%) with increased disease duration (≥ 6 -<12 m). The expression of miRNA-375 in other tissues rather than β -cells like brain, (Kloosterman *et al.*, 2007) may partially explain the specificity-association of the above results. These findings suggest that miRNAs in human serum are important disease diagnostic markers and prognostic predictors. Early detection of abnormal expression of miRNAs contributes to the diagnosis and treatment of T1D patients.

4.8 The Association of C-peptide with Other Study Biomarkers

4.8.1 Connecting Peptide, GADA and IA-2A

The correlation between the anti-GAD Abs and serum C-peptide in different study groups is shown in **Table 4.3**. The results reveal no significant differences ($p>0.05$) in the correlation between the anti-GAD Abs positive (low, moderate or high) and negative subjects with frequency % of C-peptide level among all study groups. The same was true for C-peptide mean titer. In T1D groups, the regression analysis in **Figure 4.8** showed a minor positive correlation between anti-GAD Abs level and C-peptide level with no significant differences ($p>0.05$). The same was true for FDRs group. For HC group there is a negative association between anti-GAD Abs level and C-peptide level with no significant differences ($p>0.05$).

Table (4.3): Correlation between anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody and connecting peptide in all study groups

Parameters			Connecting peptide (ng/ml)								p. value	
			Below N (<3)		Normal (3-6)		Above N (>6)		Total			
			FR (%)	Mean	FR (%)	Mean	FR (%)	Mean	FR (%)	Mean		
Anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody (U/ml)	T1D (n=35)	Positive	L (n=7)	4(57.1)	1.6	3 (42.9)	3.9	0(0)	0	7(100)	2.6	p=0.07
			M (n=4)	3 (75)	1.7	1 (25)	5.2	0(0)	0	4(100)	2.6	
			H (n=20)	13(65)	1.9	6(30)	3.8	1(5)	7.2	20(100)	2.7	
			T (n=31)	20(64.5)	1.8	10(32.3)	4	1(3.2)	7.2	31(100)	2.7	
		-ve (n=4)	3(75)	2.1	1(25)	3.2	0(0)	0	4(100)	2.4		
		Total (n=35)	23(65.7)	1.8	11(31.4)	3.9	1(2.9)	7.2	35(100)	2.6		
	FDR (n=35)	Positive	L (n=3)	0(0)	0	3(100)	4	0(0)	0	3(100)	4	p=0.3
			M (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	
			H (n=1)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	1(100)	6.9	1(100)	6.9	
			T (n=4)	0(0)	0	3(75)	4	1(25)	6.9	4(100)	4.7	
		-ve (n=31)	3(9.7)	2.3	12(38.7)	4	16(51.6)	7	31(100)	5.4		
		Total (n=35)	3(8.6)	2.3	15(42.8)	4	17(48.6)	7	35(100)	5.3		
	HC (n=20)	Positive	L (n=1)	0(0)	0	1(100)	3.7	0(0)	0	1(100)	3.7	P=0.1
			M (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	
			H (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	
T (n=1)			0(0)	0	1(100)	3.7	0(0)	0	1(100)	3.7		
-ve (n=19)		1(5.3)	2.8	5(26.3)	5.2	13(68.4)	7.5	19(100)	6.6			
Total (n=20)		1(5)	2.8	6 (30)	5	13(65)	7.5	20(100)	6.5			

N=normal, n=number, L=low (5-20 U/ml), M=moderate (21-50 U/ml), H=high (>50 U/ml), FR=frequency, -ve=negative and T=total.

Figure (4.8): Regression analysis of anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody and connecting peptide in all study groups

In Table 4.4, the correlation between IA-2A and C-peptide in all study groups is shown. For positive IA-2A within T1D and FDRS groups, the results revealed that 12/14 (85.7%) and 3/4 (75%), respectively, were with below normal C-peptide level with a total mean titer of 2.1 ng/ml and 2.6 ng/ml, respectively, whereas the negative IA-2A were 11/21 (52.4%) and 0/31 (0%), respectively, had below normal C-peptide level with a total mean titer 3 ng/ml and 5.6 ng/ml, respectively. The differences between positive and negative IA-2A regarded to C-peptide level were significant ($p < 0.05$).

In the HC group, the above normal level of C-peptide was the highest among negative IA-2A 13/19 (68.4%) compared to the positive IA-2A 0/1 (0%). The difference between positive and negative IA-2A was significant ($p < 0.05$). The mean titer for serum C-peptide was highest in negative IA-2A (6.6 ng/ml) compared to positive IA-2A (4.3 ng/ml) with significant difference ($P < 0.05$).

Table (4.4): Correlation between islet antigen-2 antibody and connecting peptide in all study groups

Parameters			Connecting peptide (ng/ml)								P-value
			Below N (<3)		Normal (3-6)		Above N (>6)		Total		
			FR (%)	M	FR (%)	M	FR (%)	M	FR (%)	M	
Islet antigen-2 antibody	T1D (n=35)	+ve (n=14)	12(85.7)	1.8	2(14.3)	3.6	0(0)	0	14(100)	2.1	P=0.02
		-ve (n=21)	11(52.4)	1.8	9(42.8)	3.9	1(4.8)	7.2	21(100)	3	
		T(n=35)	23(65.7)	1.8	11(31.4)	3.9	1(2.9)	7.2	35(100)	2.6	
	FDR (n=35)	+ve (n=4)	3(75)	2.3	1(25)	3.5	0(0)	0	4(100)	2.6	P=0.01
		-ve (n=31)	0(0)	0	14(45.2)	4	7(54.8)	7	31(100)	5.6	
		T(n=35)	3(8.6)	2.3	15(42.8)	4	7(48.6)	7	35(100)	5.3	
	HC (n=20)	+ve (n=1)	0(0)	0	1(100)	4.3	0(0)	0	1(100)	4.3	P=0.03
		-ve (n=19)	1(5.3)	2.8	5(26.3)	5.1	13(68.4)	7.5	19(100)	6.6	
		T(n=20)	1(5)	2.8	6(30)	5	13(65)	7.5	20(100)	6.5	

N=normal, FR=frequency, +ve=positive, -ve=negative, T=total, n=number and M=mean.

Several studies have demonstrated the correlation of auto-Abs, mainly GADA and IA-2A, with the temporal changes in residual β -cells function and mass (as expressed by C-peptide levels in this study) after diagnosis of T1D. Conflicting findings have been reported in various studies, revealing either no association ([Sabbah et al., 1999](#)), negative association ([Decochez et al., 2000](#)), or a positive association ([Ten et al., 2016](#)). The present study showed no significant differences in C-peptide level between GADA positive and GADA negative subjects among all study groups ([Table 4.3 and Figure 4.8](#)). These conflicting results may be due to differences in patient selection criteria (e.g., age at diagnosis) and in the methods of the biomarkers measurement or any other unknown reasons.

[Table 4.4](#) results are fully coordinated with [Christie et al., \(2002\)](#) report, who found IA-2A positivity to be correlated with an obvious reduction in residual β -cells function in T1D and the presence of IA-2A is

to be associated with lower serum C-peptide levels. Many possible explanations for the decreased level of C-peptide among the IA-2A positive in comparison to IA-2A negative subjects; first, insulinoma-associated protein 2 (IA-2 and IA-2 β) play a major role in insulin secretion in which the deletion of IA-2 and/or IA-2 β lead to reduction in insulin content and secretion which is due to a reduction in the number of dense core vesicle (Cai *et al.*, 2011). Second, the presence of IA-2A in particular, which is often associated with other Abs, confers a higher risk of rapid development toward clinical onset than multiple Abs. It was proposed that the production of IA-2A coincides with a critical shift in T1D progression, where the intracellular domain of IA-2 may only become encountered with the immune system at the outer cell surface in the case of β -cells damage or dysfunction (Herawati *et al.*, 2017).

4.8.2 Connecting Peptide and Total Antioxidant Capacity

Table 4.5 illustrates the relationship between serum C-peptide level and serum TAC level. The difference in the frequency % of TAC level between subjects with below normal, normal and above normal level of serum C-peptide was not significant ($p>0.05$) for all study groups. The same results profile was documented with TAC mean titer as it is clear in the table.

The results of the present study (Figure 4.9) identified a simple positive correlation ($p>0.05$) between serum C-peptide and TAC level in T1D and HC groups, while the results of FDRs groups showed the opposite without a significant difference ($p>0.05$).

Table (4.5): Correlation between connecting peptide and total antioxidant capacity in all study groups

Parameters			Total antioxidant capacity (mM)					p. value	
			Below N (<0.5)		Normal (0.5-2)		Total		
			FR(%)	Mean	FR(%)	Mean	FR(%)		Mean
Connecting peptide (ng/ml)	T1D (n=35)	Below N (n=23)	18(78.3)	0.38	5(21.7)	0.56	23(100)	0.42	P=0.09
		Normal (n=11)	11(100)	0.4	0(0)	0	11(100)	0.4	
		Above N (n=1)	1(100)	0.44	0(0)	0	1(100)	0.44	
		Total (n=35)	30(85.7)	0.39	5(14.3)	0.56	35(100)	0.42	
	FDR (n=35)	Below N (n=3)	1(33.3)	0.49	2(66.7)	0.53	3(100)	0.52	P=0.2
		Normal (n=15)	11(73.3)	0.42	4(26.7)	0.59	15(100)	0.46	
		Above N (n=17)	11(64.7)	0.44	6(35.3)	0.56	17(100)	0.48	
		Total (n=35)	23(65.7)	0.43	12(34.3)	0.56	35(100)	0.48	
	HC (n=20)	Below N (n=1)	0(0)	0	1(100)	0.52	1(100)	0.52	P=0.1
		Normal (n=6)	4(66.7)	0.4	2(33.3)	0.53	6(100)	0.45	
		Above N (n=13)	8(61.5)	0.4	5(38.5)	0.56	13(100)	0.46	
		Total (n=20)	12(60)	0.4	8(40)	0.54	20(100)	0.46	

FR=frequency, n=number, N=normal, **Below N** (<3 ng/ml), **Normal** (3-6 ng/ml) and **Above N** (>6 ng/ml).

Figure (4.9): Regression analysis of connecting peptide and total antioxidant capacity in all study groups

The results of the current study showed no significant difference in TAC level in relation to C-peptide level in all study groups (Table 4.5 and Figure 4.9). This result was unusual when compared with the potential

adverse effects of OS on β -cells (Keane *et al.*, 2015). Disruption of normal β -cells function in response to OS has been observed in a previous study (Zraika *et al.*, 2006). A possible explanation for this, could be due to free radicals which act as a double-edged sword in inflecting insulin signaling, being required for insulin to employ its physiological action, but also being involved in the pathogenesis of insulin resistance (Bashan *et al.*, 2009). There might be positive roles of, or a need for, ROS or RNS for the normal function of pancreatic β -cells. Evidence for such a role does exist. Thus, a luxurious study by Leloup *et al.*, (2009) exhibited that mitochondria-derived ROS are crucial for normal glucose-stimulated insulin stimulation. While antioxidants in this study were able to blunt insulin excretion, insulin release could be induced with mitochondrial complex blockers that produce ROS. Another study (Llanos *et al.*, 2015) has confirmed these findings, exhibiting that ryanodine receptor-mediated Ca_2^+ release induced by ROS is an important step in glucose-induced insulin excretion. These observations indicate that antioxidant and OS have a relatively equal role of insulin secretion by β -cells, however, in harmony with these findings, this study results illustrated no significant different in C-peptide level in correlation with TAC level.

There are still many open questions respecting the actual role of ROS and other oxidative in the advancement of disrupted glucose tolerance and more research is needed to find out their contribution to the pathophysiology as well as possibilities to modulate them in a therapeutic way. To what extent, for example, does OS affect β -cells identity and therefore function-independently of cell survival? Future studies will be required to explore this and other questions and may lead to the

identification of new ways to modulate the impact of OS for therapeutic assistance.

4.8.3 Connecting Peptide and Micro-RNA-25

The results of the correlation between C-peptide and miRNA-25 in all study groups are demonstrated in Table 4.6. The frequency % of low serum miRNA-25 level was higher (94.7% and 100%) in T1D and FDRs subjects, respectively, who had a below normal C-peptide level compared to FDRs subjects with normal-above normal C-peptide level (70.6%). These differences were significant ($p < 0.05$) when compared between the subjects with below normal and normal or above normal C-peptide level. The mean titer of serum miRNA-25 in FDRs and T1D groups exhibited a similar profile to that of the frequency % results. The T1D and FDRs subjects with below normal C-peptide level exhibited the lowest mean titer (1.1×10^6 copy/ μL^{-1} for both) of serum miRNA-25, in comparison with FDRs subjects with normal-above normal C-peptide level (1.7×10^6 copy/ μL^{-1}) with significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

No significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were detected in miRNA-25 frequency % and mean titer between subjects with below normal and normal-above normal C-peptide level among HC group.

For T1D group, significant ($p < 0.05$) increased C-peptide levels are associated with elevated miRNA-25 levels (Figure 4.10). Regarding to FDRs and HC groups, the same results profile was documented in the same figure, but without significant differences ($p > 0.05$).

Table (4.6): Correlation between connecting peptide and miRNA-25 in all study groups

Parameters			miRNA-25 (copy/ μl^{-1})								p. value
			L(<2 x 10 ⁶)		M(2-3 x 10 ⁶)		H(>3 x 10 ⁶)		Total x 10 ⁶		
			FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	
Connecting peptide (ng/ml)	T1D (n=20)	B (n=19)	18(94.7)	1	0(0)	0	1(5.3)	3.7	19(100)	1.1	P=0.00
		N-A (n=1)	0(0)	0	1(100)	2.9	0(0)	0	1(100)	2.9	
		T (n=20)	18(90)	1	1(5)	2.9	1(5)	3.7	20(100)	1.1	
	FDR (n=20)	B (n=3)	3(100)	1.1	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	3(100)	1.1	
		N-A(n=17)	12(70.6)	1	3(17.6)	2.3	2(11.8)	4.3	17(100)	1.7	
		T (n=20)	15(75)	1.1	3(15)	2.3	2(10)	4.3	20(100)	1.6	
	HC (n=10)	B (n=1)	0(0)	0	1(100)	2.3	0(0)	0	1(100)	2.3	P=0.2
		N-A(n=9)	3(33.3)	1.4	3(33.3)	2.3	3(33.4)	7.2	9(100)	3.6	
		T (n=10)	3(30)	1.4	4(40)	2.3	3(30)	7.2	10(100)	3.5	

L=low, M=moderate, H=high, B=below normal (<3 ng/ml), N=normal (3-6 ng/ml), A=above normal (>6 ng/ml), T=total, n=number and FR=frequency.

Figure (4.10): Regression analysis of connecting peptide and miRNA-25 in all study groups

Studies have shown that circulating levels of miRNA-25 were correlated to the residual β -cells function (assessed by C-peptide) and with adequate glycemic control (assessed by glycated hemoglobin) three months from T1D onset (Nielsen *et al.*, 2012). In compatibility with these findings, this study results (Table 4.6) exhibited a significant elevation of

miRNA-25 among subjects with normal or above normal C-peptide level compared to depleted miRNA-25 level among subjects with below normal C-peptide and in addition to that there is a significant positive correlation between them (Figure 4.10). These findings indicate that there was an association between miRNA-25 and residual β -cells function (as represented by C-peptide). The present study findings of improved residual β -cells function in patients with high level of miRNA-25 are in accordance with Fu *et al.*, (2010), suggesting a role of miRNA-25 on cell proliferation of the endocrine cells of the pancreas. The association of miRNA-25 with better residual β -cells function may indicate that this miRNA could be an important biomarker that could be used during early and intensive management of newly diagnosed diabetes to improve blood glucose control and reduce microvascular complications.

4.8.4 Connecting Peptide and Micro-RNA-375

The correlation of serum C-peptide with serum miRNA-375 biomarkers results are shown in Table 4.7. Among 19/20 and 3/20 with below normal C-peptide level in T1D and FDRs groups, respectively, 6/19 (31.6%) and 3/3 (100%), respectively were with high frequency % of miRNA-375. On other hand, among 17/20 and 9/10 with normal or above normal C-peptide level in FDRs and HC groups, respectively, 4/17 (23.5%) and 5/9 (55.5%), respectively were with high frequency % of miRNA-375. In comparison between the subjects with below normal and subjects with normal or above normal C-peptide level and their correlation with frequencies of miRNA-375 (except T1D X HC) there were a significant differences ($p < 0.05$). For miRNA-375 mean titer, the difference between those with below normal C-peptide level (457.6×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} (T1D) and 1450.9×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} (FDRs)) and normal or above

normal C-peptide level (391.3×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} (FDRs) and 430.9×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} (HC)) was significant ($p < 0.05$).

The results of regression analysis (Figure 4.11) showed that there was an inverse significant ($p < 0.05$) relationship between C-peptide level and miRNA-375 level in FDRs group. The same was true for T1D and HC, but without significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

Table (4.7): Correlation between connecting peptide and miRNA-375 in all study groups

Parameters			miRNA-375 (copy/ μl^{-1})								p-value
			L (<300 x 10 ⁶)		M(300-400x10 ⁶)		H (>400x10 ⁶)		Total x 10 ⁶		
			FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	
Connecting peptide (ng/ml)	T1D (n=20)	B (n=19)	6(31.6)	174.3	7(36.8)	337.6	6(31.6)	881	19(100)	457.6	P=0.00
		N-A(n=1)	1(100)	278.9	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	1(100)	278.9	
		T (n=20)	7(35)	189.2	7(35)	337.6	6(30)	881	20(100)	448.7	
	FDR (n=20)	B (n=3)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	3(100)	1450.9	3(100)	1450.9	
		N-A(n=17)	2(11.8)	292.7	11(64.7)	349.7	4(23.5)	555	17(100)	391.3	
		T (n=20)	2(10)	292.7	11(55)	349.7	7(35)	938.9	20(100)	550.2	
	HC (n=10)	B (n=1)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	1(100)	477	1(100)	477	
		N-A (n=9)	0(0)	0	4(44.5)	366.5	5(55.5)	482.4	9(100)	430.9	
		T (n=10)	0(0)	0	4(40)	366.5	6(60)	481.5	10(100)	435.5	

L=low, M=moderate, H=high, T=total, FR=frequency, n=number, B=below normal (<3 ng/ml), N=normal (3-6 ng/ml) and A=above normal (>6ng/ml).

Figure (4.11): Regression analysis of connecting peptide and miRNA-375 in all study groups

Due to miRNA-375 critical importance to β -cells integrity and function, extracellular circulating miRNA-375 levels have been reported as a biomarker of β -cells function (Song *et al.*, 2017). In β -cells islets miRNA-375 levels are decreased when high levels of glucose are available (Poy *et al.*, 2004). Low levels of miRNA-375 induce insulin secretion by de-repression of its targets myotrophin (Li *et al.*, 2010) and phosphoinositide-dependent kinase-1 (El Ouaamari *et al.*, 2008), while overexpression of miRNA-375 attenuates proliferation and insulin gene transcription while reducing glucose-induced insulin secretion (Li *et al.*, 2010). Consistent with these studies, the current study showed (Table 4.7) a significant elevation of miRNA-375 level among subjects with below normal C-peptide level compared to subjects with normal or above normal C-peptide level and the miRNA-375 level was negatively correlated with C-peptide level (Figure 4.11). Overall, it is becoming clear that miRNA-375 targets a suite of genes that negatively regulate cellular growth and proliferation (Poy *et al.*, 2009), and that aberrant loss of this miRNA leads to dramatic reduction of β -cells mass, leading to low levels of insulin, hyperglycemia, and thus diabetes.

4.9 The Association of GADA with Other Study Biomarkers

4.9.1 Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase Antibody and IA-2A

In **Table 4.8**, the association between anti-GAD Abs positivity and serum IA-2A positivity is illustrated. There was no significant association between positive (low, moderate or high levels) or negative anti-GAD Abs in the frequency of positive or negative serum IA-2A in all study groups.

Table (4.8): Association between anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody and islet antigen-2 antibody in all study groups

Parameters			Islet antigen-2 antibody						p. value	
			Positive		Negative		Total			
			FR	%	FR	%	FR	%		
Anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody (U/ml)	T1D (n=35)	Positive	L (n=7)	3	42.9	4	57.1	7	100	P=0.2
			M (n=4)	2	50	2	50	4	100	
			H (n=20)	8	40	12	60	20	100	
			Total (n=31)	13	41.9	18	58.1	31	100	
		Negative (n=4)	1	25	3	75	4	100		
		Total (n=35)	14	40	21	60	35	100		
	FDR (n=35)	Positive	L (n=3)	0	0	3	100	3	100	P=0.6
			M (n=0)	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			H (n=1)	0	0	1	100	1	100	
			Total (n=4)	0	0	4	100	4	100	
		Negative (n=31)	4	12.9	27	87.1	31	100		
		Total (n=35)	4	11.4	31	88.6	35	100		
	HC (n=20)	Positive	L (n=1)	0	0	1	100	1	100	P=0.3
			M (n=0)	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			H (n=0)	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Total (n=1)			0	0	1	100	1	100		
Negative (n=19)		1	5.3	18	94.7	19	100			
Total (n=20)		1	5	19	95	20	100			

L=low (5-20 U/ml), M=moderate (21-50 U/ml), H=high (>50 U/ml), n=number and FR=frequency.

In this study, the results in **Table 4.8** revealed no correlation between GADA positivity and IA-2A positively. Among this study patients, **41.9%** had both GADA and IA-2A. In another study **48.8%** had both auto-Abs (**Cheng et al., 2018**). In a study in Northern Taiwan, only **15.5%** of the 174 T1D patients had both GADA and IA-2A (**Chang et al., 2004**), which is lower than the current study. However, the disease duration in the last mentioned study was 4.7 years, whereas it was <1 years in the present study which would suggest that the current study results may reflect the true correlation between GADA and IA-2A more accurately.

4.9.2 Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase Antibody and TAC

Table 4.9 expresses the correlation of anti-GAD Abs with serum TAC in all study groups. Among 20/35 with high anti-GAD⁺ Abs level in T1D group, 19/20 (95%) were with below normal level of TAC with mean titer of 0.39 mM. On the other hand, 7/35 of the T1D group was with low level of anti-GAD⁺ Abs, from which 5/7 (71.4%) were with below normal level of TAC with mean titer of 0.47 mM. These results reveal a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the correlation between the high and low level of anti-GAD⁺ Abs with frequency % of below normal level of TAC. The same result was reported for TAC mean titer.

For FDRs and HC groups, the difference between those with high and low level of anti-GAD Abs in relation to TAC frequency % as well as mean titer were not significant ($p > 0.05$).

The statistical regression analysis of T1D and HC (Figure 4.12) groups showed that the level of TAC was slightly inversely correlated with the level of anti-GAD-Abs, but the differences were not significant ($p > 0.05$). For FDRs groups in the same figure the results showed a poor positive correlation between the two parameters without significant differences ($p > 0.05$).

Table (4.9): Correlation between anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody and total antioxidant capacity in all study groups

Parameters			Total antioxidant capacity (mM)						p. value
			Below N (<0.5)		Normal (0.5-2)		Total		
			FR (%)	Mean	FR (%)	Mean	FR (%)	Mean	
Anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody (U/ml)	T1D (n=35)	Positive							P=0.00
		L (n=7)	5(71.4)	0.41	2(28.6)	0.62	7(100)	0.47	
		M (n=4)	3(75)	0.37	1(25)	0.54	4(100)	0.41	
		H (n=20)	19(95)	0.39	1(5)	0.51	20(100)	0.39	
		T (n=31)	27(87.1)	0.39	4(12.9)	0.57	31(100)	0.4	
		-ve (n=4)	3(75)	0.41	1(25)	0.53	4(100)	0.44	
	Total (n=35)	30(85.7)	0.39	5(14.3)	0.55	35(100)	0.42		
	FDR (n=35)	Positive							P=0.3
		L (n=3)	3(100)	0.43	0(0)	0	3(100)	0.43	
		M (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	
		H (n=1)	0(0)	0	1(100)	0.52	1(100)	0.52	
		T (n=4)	3(75)	0.43	1(25)	0.52	4(100)	0.45	
-ve (n=31)		20(64.5)	0.43	11(35.5)	0.57	31(100)	0.48		
Total (n=35)	23(65.7)	0.43	12(34.3)	0.56	35(100)	0.48			
HC (n=20)	Positive							p=0.07	
	L (n=1)	1(100)	0.45	0(0)	0	1(100)	0.45		
	M (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0		
	H (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0		
	T (n=1)	1(100)	0.45	0(0)	0	1(100)	0.45		
	-ve (n=19)	11(57.9)	0.39	8(42.1)	0.54	19(100)	0.46		
Total (n=20)	12(60)	0.4	8(40)	0.54	20(100)	0.46			

L=low (5-20 U/ml), M=moderate (21-50 U/ml), H=high (>50 U/ml), FR=frequency, N=normal, T=total, n=number and -ve=negative.

Figure (4.12): Regression analysis of anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody and total antioxidant capacity in all study groups

Growing evidence suggests that ROS plays an important role in the initiation and progression of diabetes and its associated complications (Coughlan *et al.*, 2009). These increased levels of free radicals pose a direct toxic effect on GAD₆₅ and increase its immunogenicity (Khan *et al.*, 2009), and continuous long durations of increased levels of ROS cause an increase in antigenic determinants on GAD₆₅. So, the avidity of GAD₆₅ became more complex and gain increased strength of binding because of the interdependency of epitopes (Khan *et al.*, 2011). Consistent with the above findings, this study results showed (Table 4.9) a significant decrease in serum TAC level among patients with high GADA⁺ in comparison to low GADA⁺ patients and a slight inverse correlation between the two biomarkers (Figure 4.12). In agreement with the current study, another study showed that the mean activities of antioxidant enzymes are depleted in T1D patients with positive GADA (Mahdi *et al.*, 2015).

4.9.3 Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase Antibody and Micro-RNA-25

Table 4.10 expresses the correlation of anti-GAD Abs with the serum miRNA-25. Among 20/20 and 4/20 with positive anti-GAD Abs in T1D and FDRs groups, respectively, 18/20 (90%), and 4/4 (100%), respectively were with low frequency % of miRNA-25 level with mean titer of 1.1×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} and 1.3×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} , respectively. On the other hand, 16/20 of FDRs group was with negative anti-GAD Abs from which 11/16 (68.7%) were with low frequency % of miRNA-25 level with mean titer of 1.7×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} . These results reveal a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the correlation between the subjects with positive and negative anti-GAD Abs with miRNA-25 frequency percent. The same result was reported for miRNA-25 mean titer.

For HC groups, no significant difference ($p>0.05$) was found in the level of miRNA-25 among anti-GAD Abs positive or negative subjects.

The results of the present study showed (Figure 4.13) a clear increase in the level of miRNA-25 with an increase in the level of anti-GAD Abs among T1D group with significant difference ($p<0.05$), also the level of miRNA-25 was slightly elevated with the increased level of anti-GAD Abs among FDRs group without a significant difference ($p>0.05$). For HC group the result showed an inverse poor relationship ($p>0.05$) between both.

Table (4.10): Correlation between anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody and miRNA-25 in all study groups

Parameters			miRNA-25 (copy/ μl^{-1})							p. value			
			L (<2 x 10 ⁶)		M (2-3 x 10 ⁶)		H (>3 x 10 ⁶)		Total x 10 ⁶				
			FR (%)	Mean	FR (%)	Mean	FR (%)	Mean	FR (%)		Mean		
Anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody (U/ml)	T1D (n=20)	Positive	L (n=4)	4(100)	1.05	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	4(100)	1.05	P=0.00	
			M (n=3)	3(100)	0.85	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	3(100)	0.85		
			H (n=13)	11(84.6)	1.03	1(7.7)	2.9	1(7.7)	3.7	13(100)	1.3		
			T (n=20)	18(90)	1.01	1(5)	2.9	1(5)	3.7	20(100)	1.1		
		-ve (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0			
		Total (n=20)	18(90)	1.01	1(5)	2.9	1(5)	3.7	20(100)	1.1			
	FDR (n=20)	Positive	L (n=3)	3(100)	1.1	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	3(100)	1.1		
			M (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0		
			H (n=1)	1(100)	1.9	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	1(100)	1.9		
			T (n=4)	4(100)	1.3	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	4(100)	1.3		
		-ve (n=16)	11(68.7)	1.02	3(18.8)	2.3	2(12.5)	4.3	16(100)	1.7			
		Total (n=20)	15(75)	1.1	3(15)	2.3	2(10)	4.3	20(100)	1.6			
	HC (n=10)	Positive	L (n=1)	0(0)	0	1(100)	2.4	0(0)	0	1(100)	2.4		P=0.3
			M (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0		
			H (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0		
			T (n=1)	0(0)	0	1(100)	2.4	0(0)	0	1(100)	2.4		
		-ve (n=9)	3(33.3)	1.4	3(33.3)	2.3	3(33.4)	7.2	9(100)	1.5			
		Total (n=10)	3(30)	1.4	4(40)	2.3	3(30)	7.2	10(100)	3.5			

L=low (5-20 U/ml), M=moderate (21-50 U/ml), H=high (>50 U/ml), FR=frequency, -ve=negative, n=number and T=total.

Figure (4.13): Regression analysis of anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody and miRNA-25 in all study groups

Glutamic acid decarboxylase auto-Abs and IA-2A are now being used as a more specific cytoplasmic assay in the diagnosis of T1D (Lebastchi and Herold, 2012). The findings of the current study showed that the miRNA-25 level was significantly lower among subjects with $GADA^+$ compared to $GADA^-$ subjects of T1D and FDRs groups (Table 4.10). In harmony with this study finding, Åkerman *et al.*, (2018) found lower miRNA-25 expression in T1D patients. Another interesting finding of this study results was the significant positive association between miRNA-25 and GADA titers within T1D group (Figure 4.13). There are many possible explanations of these results; first, miRNA-25 target molecules are important regulators of autophagy, OS, inflammation, calcium handling, etc. These mechanisms could be key factors in the pathogenesis of DM (Sárközy *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, miRNA-25 was associated with apoptosis and β -cells networks (Zigang *et al.*, 2014) where it is involved in the regulation of apoptosis and cell proliferation by targeting proapoptotic proteins as Bim and Trail (TNF-related

apoptosis inducing ligand) (Razumilava *et al.*, 2012). Second, this miRNA play an important role in the regulation of inflammatory cytokine production such as TNF- α , keratinocyte-derived chemokine, and macrophage inflammatory protein-2 (Ha, 2011). Previous studies indicated that miRNA-25 might be involved in the regulation of B cells (Ota *et al.*, 2004) in which this miRNA is required for the pro-B to pre-B-cell transition during B-cell development. Indeed, expression of miRNA-25 was shown to peak in pre-B-cells, where it inhibited cell death through down regulation of the proapoptotic protein Bim (Ventura *et al.*, 2008). There are some evidences suggesting that miRNA-25 positively regulated B-cells and T cells (Lindsay, 2008). The authors of the last report speculated that the phenotypic changes after expression of miRNA-25 resulted in breakdown in peripheral T-cell tolerance, expansion of the CD4⁺ T cells that activates B cells, leading to the development of autoimmunity. To the best of our knowledge, there are no previous studies reporting associations between islet auto-Abs and miRNA-25 expression in serum from high-risk individuals or T1D patients.

4.9.4 Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase Antibody and Micro-RNA-375

The correlation between anti-GAD Abs (positive or negative) and miRNA-375 level in all study groups is listed in Table 4.11. There were no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in the frequency % as well as mean titer of miRNA-375 among both positive and negative anti-GAD-Abs subjects in all study groups.

In T1D group, data from Figure 4.14 indicated a poor ($p > 0.05$) positive correlation between the anti-GAD Abs and miRNA-375 levels, whereas, FDRs and HC groups revealed an inversed correlation in the same figure without a significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

Table (4.11): Correlation between anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody and miRNA-375 in all study groups

Parameters			miRNA-375 (copy/ μl^{-1})								p. value	
			L (<300 $\times 10^6$)		M(300-400 $\times 10^6$)		H (>400 $\times 10^6$)		Total $\times 10^6$			
			FR(%)	Mean	FR(%)	Mean	FR(%)	Mean	FR(%)	Mean		
Anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody (U/ml)	T1D (n=20)	Positive	L (n=4)	0(0)	0	1(25)	355	3(75)	421.8	4(100)	405.1	P=0.1
		M (n=3)	2(66.7)	70.4	1(33.3)	346.1	0(0)	0	3(100)	162.3		
		H (n=13)	5(38.5)	236.8	5(38.5)	332.5	3(23)	1340.3	13(100)	528.3		
		T (n=20)	7(35)	189.3	7(35)	337.6	6(30)	881.1	20(100)	488.7		
		-ve (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0		
		Total (n=20)	7(35)	189.3	7(35)	337.6	6(30)	881.1	20(100)	488.7		
	FDR (n=20)	Positive	L (n=3)	0(0)	0	2(66.7)	369.3	1(33.3)	932.1	3(100)	556.9	
		M (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0		
		H (n=1)	1(100)	289.8	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	1(100)	289.8		
		T (n=4)	1(25)	289.8	2(50)	369.3	1(25)	932.1	4(100)	490.1		
		-ve (n=16)	1(6.2)	295.7	9(56.3)	345.4	6(37.5)	940.1	16(100)	565.3		
		Total (n=20)	2(10)	292.7	11(55)	349.7	7(35)	938.9	20(100)	550.2		
	HC (n=10)	Positive	L (n=1)	0(0)	0	1(100)	364.8	0(0)	0	1(100)	364.8	
		M (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0		
		H (n=0)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	0(0)	0		
		T (n=1)	0(0)	0	1(100)	364.8	0(0)	0	1(100)	364.8		
		-ve (n=9)	0(0)	0	3(33.3)	367.1	6(66.7)	481.5	9(100)	443.4		
		Total (n=10)	0(0)	0	4(40)	366.5	6(60)	481.5	10(100)	435.5		

L=low (5-20 U/ml), M=moderate (21-50 U/ml), H=high (>50 U/ml), FR=frequency, T=total, n=number and -ve=negative.

Figure (4.14): Regression analysis of anti-glutamic acid decarboxylase antibody and miRNA-375 in all study groups

The contribution of miRNAs to the development of human T1D has been largely unexplored. More particularly, their use as biomarkers to monitor the fate and/or function of the pancreatic β -cells is attractive. In this study we found no significant differences in serum miRNA-375 level between GADA⁺ and GADA⁻ individuals among all study groups. In agreement with this study finding, another study also reported no association between serum miRNA-375 and GADA concentrations (Marchand *et al.*, 2016).

4.10 The Association of IA-2A with Other Study Biomarkers

4.10.1 Islet Antigen-2 Antibody and Total Antioxidant Capacity

In Table 4.12, the correlation between IA-2A positivity and serum TAC is illustrated. There was no significant difference between positive or negative IA-2A in the frequency of below normal or normal level as well as mean titer of serum TAC.

Table (4.12): Correlation between islet antigen-2 antibody and total antioxidant capacity in all study groups

Parameters			Total antioxidant capacity (mM)				p. value		
			Below N(<0.5)		Normal (0.5-2)			Total	
			FR (%)	Mean	FR (%)	Mean		FR (%)	Mean
Islet antigen-2 antibody	T1D (n=35)	+ve (n=14)	11(78.6)	0.38	3(21.4)	0.59	14(100)	0.43	P=0.6
		-ve (n=21)	19(90.5)	0.4	2(9.5)	0.52	21(100)	0.41	
		T (n=35)	30(85.7)	0.39	5(14.3)	0.56	35(100)	0.42	
	FDR (n=35)	+ve (n=4)	1(25)	0.49	3(75)	0.53	4(100)	0.52	P=0.2
		-ve (n=31)	22(71)	0.43	9(29)	0.57	31(100)	0.47	
		T (n=35)	23(65.7)	0.43	12(34.3)	0.56	35(100)	0.48	
	HC (n=20)	+ve (n=1)	1(100)	0.44	0(0)	0	1(100)	0.44	P=0.8
		-ve (n=19)	11(57.9)	0.4	8(42.1)	0.54	19(100)	0.46	
		T (n=20)	12(60)	0.4	8(40)	0.54	20(100)	0.46	

N=normal, FR=frequency, +ve=positive, -ve=negative, n=number and T=total.

A previous study demonstrated the specific modification of the major islet auto-Ags GAD by metal-catalysed oxidation to generate novel epitopes which could be recognized by the immune system and help to drive the autoimmune response leading to β -cells destruction and T1D

development (Trigwell *et al.*, 2001). Consistent with this possibility, it was previously illustrated in this study (Table 4.9) a significant decrease in serum TAC level among patients with high GADA⁺ level in comparison to low GADA⁺ level and there is a slight inverse correlation between the two biomarkers (Figure 4.12). The oxidatively modified forms of GAD were recognized by T1D patient's auto-Abs. The modification by ROS observed with GAD did not occur with other islet Ags like IA-2 (Trigwell *et al.*, 2001). Consistent with these findings, this study results showed no significant difference in serum TAC level between IA-2A⁺ and IA-2A⁻ individuals (Table 4.12) as the result comes in accordance with Mahdi *et al.*, (2015) that recorded that the mean activities of antioxidative enzymes were depleted in patients with T1D (positive GADA only not to other auto-Abs). Overall, the results presented here are consistent with a role for ROS in the autoimmune response to islet β -cells in T1D by oxidatively modifying potential islet auto-Ags. As demonstrated here, this process may be relatively specific for GAD compared with IA-2 or other islet proteins.

4.10.2 Islet Antigen-2 Antibody and Micro-RNA-25

Table 4.13 demonstrates the correlation of IA-2A positivity and IA-2A negativity with serum miRNA-25 level. All IA-2A positive subjects in T1D, FDRs and HC groups, were with low frequency % of miRNA-25 and mean titer of 0.75×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} , 1×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} , and 1.7×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} , respectively. In IA-2A negative subjects, the frequency % of low level of miRNA-25 was lower among T1D 8/10 (80%), FDRs 11/16 (68.7%), and HC 2/9 (22.2%) groups with higher mean titer, 1.7×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} , 1.7×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} and 3.7×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} , respectively, in comparison to IA-2A positive subjects. The difference in the frequency %

and the mean titers between IA-2A positive and IA-2A negative were significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table (4.13): Correlation between islet antigen-2 antibody and miRNA-25 in all study groups

Parameters			miRNA-25 (copy/ μl^{-1})								p. value
			L (<2 x 10 ⁶)		M (2-3 x 10 ⁶)		H (>3 x 10 ⁶)		Total x 10 ⁶		
			FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	FR%	Mean	FR%	Mean	
Islet antigen-2 antibody	T1D (n=20)	+ve (n=10)	10(100)	0.75	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	10(100)	0.75	P=0.02
		-ve (n=10)	8(80)	1.1	1(10)	2.9	1(10)	3.7	10(100)	1.7	
		T (n=20)	18(90)	1	1(5)	2.9	1(5)	3.7	20(100)	1.1	
	FDR (n=20)	+ve (n=4)	4(100)	1	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	4(100)	1	P=0.01
		-ve (n=16)	11(68.7)	1.1	3(18.8)	2.3	2(12.5)	4.3	16(100)	1.7	
		T (n=20)	15(75)	1.1	3(15)	2.3	2(10)	4.3	20(100)	1.6	
	HC (n=10)	+ve (n=1)	1(100)	1.7	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	1(100)	1.7	P=0.00
		-ve (n=9)	2(22.2)	1.2	4(44.5)	2.3	3(33.3)	7.2	9(100)	3.7	
		T (n=10)	3(30)	1.4	4(40)	2.3	3(30)	7.2	10(100)	3.5	

L=low, M=moderate, H=high, FR=frequency, T=total, +ve=positive, n=number and -ve=negative.

As previously reviewed in this thesis, GADA and IA-2A are being used as a more specific cytoplasmic assay in the diagnosis of T1D (Lebastchi and Herold, 2012). The presence of IA-2A in particular, which is often associated with other Abs, confers a higher risk of rapid progression toward clinical onset than multiple Abs (Herawati *et al.*, 2017). It is suggested that the production of IA-2A coincides with a critical switch in disease progression, where the intracellular domain of IA-2 may only become visible to the immune system at the outer cell surface in the case of β -cells damage or dysfunction (Pihoker *et al.*, 2005). These findings indicate that the presence of IA-2A is associated with massive β -cells stress/death. The results of the current study (Table 4.6) revealed that the level of miRNA-25 positively correlated with residual β -cells function (as represented by C-peptide level). In agreement with these evidences, this study results (Table 4.13) manifested a significant negative association between IA-2A positivity and miRNA-25 level. Overall, these findings confirm the possible negative role of IA-2A

on β -cells as it is reflected by low miRNA-25 level among IA-2A positive subjects.

4.10.3 Islet Antigen-2 Antibody and Micro-RNA-375

The correlation of IA-2A with serum miRNA-375 is illustrated in [Table 4.14](#). Regarding to FDRs group, the high level of miRNA-375 was higher in frequency % among IA-2A positive subjects (75%) than IA-2A negative subjects (25%) with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$). IA-2A positive subjects exhibited the highest mean titer of serum miRNA-375 ($1166.5 \times 10^6 \text{ copy}/\mu\text{l}^{-1}$) in comparison with IA-2A negative subjects ($396.2 \times 10^6 \text{ copy}/\mu\text{l}^{-1}$) with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

No significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were detected in the frequency % and mean titer of serum miRNA-375 between IA-2A positive and IA-2A negative subjects among T1D and HC groups.

Table (4.14): Correlation between islet antigen-2 antibody and miRNA-375 in all study groups

Parameters			miRNA-375 (copy/ μl^{-1})								P-value
			L(<300x10 ⁶)		M(300-400x10 ⁶)		H(>400 x 10 ⁶)		Total x 10 ⁶		
			FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	FR%	Mean	FR%	Mean	
Islet antigen-2 antibody	T1D (n=20)	+ve(n=10)	4(40)	172.7	4(40)	334.6	2(20)	420.5	10(100)	287	P=0.2
		-ve (n=10)	3(30)	211.3	3(30)	341.6	4(40)	911.3	10(100)	490.4	
		T (n=20)	7(35)	189.2	7(35)	337.6	6(30)	881	20(100)	448.7	
	FDR (n=20)	+ve (n=4)	0(0)	0	1(25)	313.6	3(75)	1450.9	4(100)	1166.5	P=0.03
		-ve (n=16)	2(12.5)	292.7	10(62.5)	353.4	4(25)	555	16(100)	396.2	
		T (n=20)	2(10)	292.7	11(55)	349.7	7(35)	938.9	20(100)	550.2	
	HC (n=10)	+ve (n=1)	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	1(100)	451.8	1(100)	451.8	P=0.4
		-ve (n=9)	0(0)	0	4(44.5)	366.5	5(55.5)	487.5	9(100)	433.7	
		T (n=10)	0(0)	0	4(40)	366.5	6(60)	481.5	10(100)	435.5	

L=low, M=moderate, H=high, FR=frequency, +ve=positive, -ve=negative, n=number and T=total.

The above table shows that the serum miRNA-375 level did not alter in the presence or absence of IA-2A positivity among T1D and HC groups, whereas it was positively correlated with IA-2A positivity in FDRs group. In consistent with these findings, another study ([Bertocchini et al., 2019](#)) observed that IA-2A-positive FDRs subjects showed a significantly

increased level of miRNA-375 compared to T1D patients and controls. Moreover, this study observed that increased circulating miRNA-375 associated with later onset of diabetes, suggesting a greater β -cells residual function. Interestingly, another study showed that miRNA-375 levels were lower in children with newly diagnosed T1D compared to age-matched control individuals (Marchand *et al.*, 2016). These data suggest that circulating miRNA-375 levels may reflect the amount of viable β -cells that are under autoimmune attack; thus, the closer to diagnosis, the lower miRNA-375 levels are.

4.11 Total Antioxidant Capacity and Micro-RNA-375

Table 4.15 expresses the correlation of TAC with miRNA-375 in all study groups. Among 16/20 subjects with below normal TAC level of T1D group, 7/16 (43.8%) were with low miRNA-375 frequency %. On the other hand, among 4/20 subjects with normal TAC level, 0/4 (0%) were with low miRNA-375 frequency %. For FDRs group, among 12/20 subjects with below normal TAC level, 3/12 (25%) were with high miRNA-375 frequency %. On the other hand, among 8/20 subjects with normal TAC level, 4/8 (50%) were with high miRNA-375 frequency %. The differences in miRNA-375 frequency % between the subjects with below normal and normal TAC were significant ($p < 0.05$).

In T1D and FDRs groups, the mean titer of serum miRNA-375 was lower ($491.1 \times 10^6 \text{ copy}/\mu\text{l}^{-1}$) and ($423.9 \times 10^6 \text{ copy}/\mu\text{l}^{-1}$) respectively, among subjects with below normal TAC level in comparison to highest level ($721.4 \times 10^6 \text{ copy}/\mu\text{l}^{-1}$ and $739.8 \times 10^6 \text{ copy}/\mu\text{l}^{-1}$, respectively) in subjects with normal TAC level with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Healthy control group results of frequency % reveal no significant correlation between serum miRNA-375 and serum TAC. The same result was reported for miRNA-375 mean titer.

In T1D and FDRs groups, the results of regression analysis (Figure 4.15) showed a positive non-significant ($p>0.05$) correlation between serum TAC and serum miRNA-375. For HC group within the same figure, the result revealed a negative non-significant ($p>0.05$) relationship between both biomarkers.

Table (4.15): Correlation between total antioxidant capacity and miRNA-375 in all study groups

Parameters			miRNA-375 (copy/ μl^{-1})								p-value
			L(<300x10 ⁶)		M(300-400x10 ⁶)		H(>400x 10 ⁶)		Total x 10 ⁶		
			FR%	Mean	FR%	Mean	FR%	Mean	FR %	Mean	
Total antioxidant capacity (mM)	T1D (n=20)	B (n=16)	7(43.8)	189.2	4(25)	333.7	5(31.2)	626.8	16(100)	491.1	P=0.00
		N (n=4)	0(0)	0	3(75)	342.8	1(25)	953.3	4(100)	721.4	
		T (n=20)	7(35)	189.2	7(35)	337.6	6(30)	881	20(100)	448.7	
	FDR (n=20)	B (n=12)	1(8.3)	295.7	8(66.7)	357	3(25)	644.9	12(100)	423.9	P=0.00
		N (n=8)	1(12.5)	289.8	3(37.5)	330.4	4(50)	1159.5	8(100)	739.8	
		T (n=20)	2(10)	292.7	11(55)	349.7	7(35)	938.9	20(100)	550.2	
	HC (n=10)	B (n=6)	0(0)	0	2(33.3)	367.9	4(66.7)	454.7	6(100)	425.8	P=0.06
		N (n=4)	0(0)	0	2(50)	365.1	2(50)	535.1	4(100)	450.1	
		T (n=10)	0(0)	0	4(40)	366.5	6(60)	481.5	10(100)	435.5	

L=low, M=moderate, H=high, T=total, FR=frequency, n=number, B=below normal (<0.5 mM) and N=normal (0.5-2 mM).

Figure (4.15): Regression analysis of total antioxidant capacity and miRNA-375 in all study groups

Hyperglycemia, a hallmark of diabetic disease, declines natural antioxidants and promotes the generation of ROS, which has the power to react with all biological components like lipids, proteins, carbohydrates, and DNA and produce toxic actions on cellular activities (Dincer *et al.*, 2002). Glucose has long been recognized to increase the cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) content of pancreatic β -cells (Tengholm, 2012). Previous studies have identified miRNA-375 as a target of cAMP in which cAMP inhibit miRNA-375 transcription. There are two major proteins that directly bind cAMP in pancreatic β -cells and mediate its effects. One of these is EPAC2 (exchange protein directly activated by cAMP 2), which works by stimulating the exocytotic machinery (Ozaki *et al.*, 2000). The other one is PKA (protein kinase A), which phosphorylates and stimulates many proteins that regulate secretion (Seino and Shibasaki, 2005) as well as proteins that regulate gene expression, e.g. CREB (cAMP response element binding protein)

(Rosenberg *et al.*, 2002). One or both of these pathways may target miRNA-375 and inhibit its expression (Keller *et al.*, 2012). The former report concludes that cAMP represses miRNA-375 through the PKA pathway. Interestingly, OS and ROS has been implicated in the cAMP independent activation of PKA (Eisel *et al.*, 2013). Conciding with these evidences this study results (Table 4.15) exhibited significant depletion in the expression of miRNA-375 among subjects with below normal TAC level than elevated expression among subjects with normal TAC level and this miRNA expression level was positively associated with TAC level (Figure 4.15) within T1D and FDRs groups.

4.12 Total Antioxidant Capacity and Micro-RNA-25

In Table 4.16, the correlation between TAC and miRNA-25 in all study groups is illustrated. For T1D and FDRs groups, the frequency % of low miRNA-25 was higher with significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the subjects with normal TAC level (100% and 87.5%, respectively) when compared with subjects with below normal TAC level (87.5% and 66.7%, respectively). The results of miRNA-25 mean titer were in a similar profile to frequency %, mean titer was higher (1.3×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} and 1.9×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} , respectively) among subjects with below normal TAC with significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in comparison to subjects with normal TAC level (1×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} and 1.1×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} , respectively). For HC group, the frequency % of low miRNA-25 was higher with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the subjects with below normal TAC level (50%) when compared with subjects with normal TAC level (0%). The results of miRNA-25 mean titer were in a similar profile to frequency %, mean titer was higher (5.5×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1}) among subjects with normal TAC with significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in

comparison to subjects with below normal TAC level (2.2×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1}).

The results of the present study (Figures 4.16) identified a negative correlation ($p>0.05$) between serum TAC and serum miRNA-25 levels in T1D and FDRs groups, while the results of HC groups in the same figure showed a positive correlation, but without significant difference ($p>0.05$).

Table (4.16): Correlation between total antioxidant capacity and miRNA-25 in all study groups

Parameters			miRNA-25 (copy/ μl^{-1})								p. value
			L (< 2×10^6)		M ($2-3 \times 10^6$)		H (> 3×10^6)		Total $\times 10^6$		
			FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	
Total antioxidant capacity (mM)	T1D (n=20)	B (n=16)	4(87.5)	0.9	1(6.3)	2.9	1(6.2)	3.7	16(100)	1.3	P=0.00
		N (n=4)	4(100)	1	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	4(100)	1	
		T (n=20)	18(90)	1	1(5)	2.9	1(5)	3.7	20(100)	1.1	
	FDR (n=20)	B (n=12)	8(66.7)	1.2	2(16.7)	2.2	2(16.6)	4.3	12(100)	1.9	P=0.00
		N (n=8)	7(87.5)	0.9	1(12.5)	2.6	0(0)	0	8(100)	1.1	
		T (n=20)	15(75)	1.1	3(15)	2.3	2(10)	4.3	20(100)	1.6	
	HC (n=10)	B (n=6)	3(50)	1.4	1(16.7)	2.4	2(33.3)	3.3	6(100)	2.2	P=0.00
		N (n=4)	0(0)	0	3(75)	2.3	1(25)	15.2	4(100)	5.5	
		T (n=10)	3(30)	1.4	4(40)	2.3	3(30)	7.2	10(100)	3.5	

L=low, M=moderate, H=high, T=total, FR=frequency, n=number, B=below normal (<0.5 mM) and N=normal (0.5-2 mM).

Figure (4.16): Regression analysis of total antioxidant capacity and miRNA-25 in all study groups

Several studies have found that the expression profile of miRNAs could be regulated by OS and mediate the pathogenic effect of ROS in some diseases and animal models, which deepens the understanding of redox biology and implicates new therapeutic strategies for OS-related diseases (Zhang *et al.*, 2014). Previous studies have reported that OS can regulate gene expression by promoting DNA demethylation (Gu *et al.*, 2013). In this study, miRNA-25 level was significantly higher in subjects with below normal TAC level in comparison to lower levels in subjects with normal TAC level for T1D and FDRs groups and the two parameters were inversely correlated. Matching our findings, another study verified that OS induced miRNA-25 generation by demethylating its promoter region through suppression the expression of DNA methyltransferases, thus demethylating the promoter region of miRNA-25 (Shi *et al.*, 2016).

4.13 The Correlation between Micro-RNA-375 and Micro-RNA-25

The correlation between serum miRNA-375 and miRNA-25 in all study groups is listed in Table 4.17. The frequency % of low serum miRNA-25 level was higher 6/6 (100%) and 7/7 (100%) in T1D subjects with high and moderate miRNA-375 level, respectively. The difference was significant ($P < 0.05$) in comparison to subjects with low miRNA-375 level 5/7 (71.4%). For mean titer, the results revealed that the mean titer of miRNA-25 was higher among subjects with low miRNA-375 level (1.7×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1}) when compared to subjects with moderate and high miRNA-375 level (1.1×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} and 1×10^6 copy/ μl^{-1} , respectively) with significant different ($p < 0.05$).

No significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were detected in miRNA-25 frequency % and mean titer between subjects with low and moderate or high miRNA-375 level among FDRs group.

The HC subjects with moderate miRNA-375 level exhibited the highest frequency % of high level miRNA-25 (50%) in comparison to subjects with high miRNA-375 level (16.7%) with significant difference ($p < 0.05$). The same was true for mean titer as documented in the table.

The regression analysis in Figure 4.17 showed an inverse correlation between serum miRNA-375 level and serum miRNA-25 level with no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) among all study groups.

Table (4.17): Correlation between miRNA-375 and miRNA-25 in all study groups

Parameters			miRNA-25 (copy/ μl^{-1})								p.value
			L (<2 x 10 ⁶)		M(2-3 x 10 ⁶)		H (>3 x 10 ⁶)		Total x 10 ⁶		
			FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	FR %	Mean	
miRNA-375 (copy/ μl^{-1})	T1D (n=20)	L (n=7)	5(71.4)	0.7	1(14.3)	2.9	1(14.3)	3.7	7(100)	1.7	P=0.00
		M (n=7)	7(100)	1.1	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	7(100)	1.1	
		H (n=6)	6(100)	1	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	6(100)	1	
		T (n=20)	18(90)	1	1(5)	2.9	1(5)	3.7	20(100)	1.1	
	FDR (n=20)	L (n=2)	2(100)	1.6	0(0)	0	0(0)	0	2(100)	1.6	P=0.09
		M (n=11)	8(72.7)	0.9	1(9.1)	2.3	2(18.2)	4.3	11(100)	1.6	
		H (n=7)	5(71.4)	1.1	2(28.6)	2.4	0(0)	0	7(100)	1.4	
		T (n=20)	15(75)	1.1	3(15)	2.3	2(10)	4.3	20(100)	1.6	
	HC (n=10)	M (n=4)	0(0)	0	2(50)	2.4	2(50)	9.1	4(100)	5.8	P=0.00
		H (n=6)	3(50)	1.4	2(33.3)	2.2	1(16.7)	3.5	6(100)	2	
		T (n=10)	3(30)	1.4	4(40)	2.3	3(30)	7.2	10(100)	3.5	

L=low (<300 x 10⁶ copy/ μl^{-1}), M=moderate (300-400 x 10⁶ copy/ μl^{-1}), H=high (>400 x 10⁶ copy/ μl^{-1}), T=total, n=number and FR=frequency.

Figure (4.17): Regression analysis of miRNA-375 and miRNA-25 in all study groups

This study results (Table 4.17) expressed a significant elevation of miRNA-25 among members with low level of miRNA-375 in comparison to depleted level among members with moderate-high miRNA-375 level and the two biomarkers were inversely associated (Figure 4.17). MicroRNA-25 was negatively associated with the HbA1c level and positively associated with stimulated C-peptide levels among new onset T1D patients (Nielsen *et al.*, 2012). In serum samples from children with new-onset T1D and age-matched HC, residual β -cells function and glycemic control after 3 months of clinical disease were associated with miRNA-25 overexpression (Stankov *et al.*, 2013), whereas miRNA-375 overexpression associated with decreased β -cells function and insulin secretion because this miRNA negatively regulates insulin gene and β -cells mass (Marchand *et al.*, 2016), therefore we postulate that the negative correlation between miRNA-375 and miRNA-25 is due to their opposite role in the regulation of β -cells function and insulin excretion.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

1. GADA is a sensitive auto-Abs biomarker, but a weak predictive biomarker for the stress/death of β -cells residual function and mass in the newly diagnosed T1D and their FDRs.
2. GADA is a vital participation in the pancreatic OS.
3. The combination of GADA, IA-2A and C-peptide could be a powerful and cost-effective pathognomonic feature for T1D and their FDRs.
4. The auto-Abs IA-2A has a better specificity and predictive power for β -cells stress and/or death amplitude during prodromal and early onset stages of T1D than GADA.
5. A significant positive association of GADA positivity and a significant negative association of IA-2A positivity with miRNA-25 expression level in T1D group. To the best of our knowledge, this the first study ever concerning this issue.
6. No association between serum miRNA-375 and GADA positivity in all study groups. Also, serum miRNA-375 level did not alter in the presence or absence of IA-2A among T1D and HC groups, whereas it was positively correlated with IA-2A positivity in FDRs group.
7. Decreased expression of miRNA-25 is a good diagnostic and predictor biomarker for new onset T1D and FDRs.
8. An increased expression among FDRs compared to a decreased expression among T1D patients of miRNA-375 may reflect β -cells residual functions at different stages of the disease.
9. The profile of expression level for both miRNA-25 and miRNA-375 could be utilized as a β -cells stress and/or death predictive biomarker. The inverse correlation of the two miRNAs in this study would help in understanding diabetic pathogenicity and reflect endogenous β -cells stress and/or death.

Conclusions and Recommendations

10. Depleted TAC level associated with low miRNA-375 and high miRNA-25 expression in T1D and their FDRs.
11. No significant difference in TAC level in relation to C-peptide level in all study groups which is an unusual result when compared with the potential adverse effects of OS on β -cells. These observations indicate that antioxidants and OS have relatively equal role in insulin secretion by β -cells.

Recommendations

1. Serum miRNA-25 measurement is recommended in the diagnosis and prediction of T1D, because of the moderate sensitivity of IA-2A and lower specificity of GADA in detection of T1D.
2. Serum miRNA-375 measurement is recommended for FDRs of T1D patients to estimate the probability of T1D development in the future.
3. Further investigations are needed to clarify the possible role of Th17 and Treg in the pathogenicity of the T1D and the equilibrium between both cells and their influential effect on fate of T1D development and their correlation with expression level of miRNA-25 and miRNA-375.
4. Further studies are needed to clarify miRNA-25, miRNA-375 and other miRNAs expression profiles in pancreatic islets or more specifically in islet-infiltrating immune cells which will shed light on their role in T1D diagnosis and management.
5. Further studies using appropriate T1D animal models are still needed to fully clarify the pathogenic role of miRNA-25 and miRNA-375 *in vivo* and evaluate their potential as therapeutic targets in T1D.

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Appendices

Appendix (I): Questionnaire data sheet

Patient №		Record №	Date	Name	Phone №
Gender		Age	Weight	Height	Occupation
Education		Disease duration	Current medication	Insulin therapy	
				Yes	No
Thyroid disease		Clinical manifestations			
Yes	No	Polyuria	Polydipsia	Polyphagia	Weight loss
№ of first degree		Vomiting	Abdominal pain	Hypertension	Others
Presence of complications					
Nephropathy		Neuropathy	Retinopathy	Others	
Family history of T1D					
Yes	No	Family member		Starting date	
Endogamy					
Yes			No		

Appendix (II): Real time polymerase chain reaction of miRNA-25

Appendix (III): Real time polymerase chain reaction of miRNA-25 standard curve samples

Appendix (IV): Real time polymerase chain reaction of miRNA-375

Appendix (V): Real time polymerase chain reaction of miRNA-375 standard curve samples

الخلاصة

ينشأ داء السكري من النوع الاول نتيجة تحطم التحمل المناعي وغزو خلايا بيتا من قبل خلايا نوع (T) النشطة ذاتياً وتحفز فقدان وظيفة خلايا بيتا وكتلتها وبالتالي العلاج لفترة طويلة الامد بالانسولين الخارجي. واحدة من أكبر التحديات العلاجية والتي في معظم الحالات تحول المرض للعلاج الجزئي فقط ولا يمكن الشفاء هو الحالة السيئة للبنكرياس عند التشخيص. مرض السكري النوع الاول لديه مراحل طويلة قبل السريرية وقد تستمر لسنوات، وخلالها تم تدمير غالبية جزر لانجرهانز خلايا بيتا (حوالي 90%). وبناء على ذلك، في وقت التشخيص خلال المرحلة السريرية، تكون أعدادا قليلة جداً قد تبقت من خلايا بيتا المنتجة للانسولين والتي تستوجب توجيه العلاج كلياً نحو العلاج بالهرمونات البديلة. اختبرت العديد من الدراسات والتجارب لوقف تدهور خلايا بيتا و/أو التنبؤ بذلك من خلال بعض المؤشرات أو المعلمات الحيوية ولكن للأسف من دون استخدام. أستهدفت هذه الدراسة كشف القدرة التنبؤية ودرجة ارتباط العوامل الحيوية الاعتيادية شبة الخاصة بداء السكري النوع الاول (GADA و IA-2A) والمؤشرات الحيوية غير المتخصصة بداء السكري النوع الاول مثل (TAC) والمؤشرات الحيوية غير التقليدية وغير المعروفة (miRNA-25 و miRNA-375) مع اجهاد او موت خلايا بيتا لدى مرضى داء السكري النوع الاول واقرباء الدرجة الاولى. شملت الدراسة 35 مريضاً بداء السكري النوع الاول (17 ذكر و 18 انثى) و 35 فرداً من اقرباء الدرجة الاولى (22 ذكر و 13 انثى) ممن يراجعون مركز السكري والغدد الصماء التخصصي في محافظة ذي قار خلال الفترة بين ايار 2018 وتشرين الثاني 2018، بمدى عمر 10-18 سنة و 4-39 سنة، على التوالي، و 20 فرداً من الاصحاء ظاهرياً (10 ذكر و 10 انثى) بمدى عمر 5-30 سنة. تم تقييم المستوى المصلي ل (GADA و IA-2A و C-peptide و TAC) ومستوى التعبير ل

(miRNA-25 و miRNA-375) لجميع افراد الدراسة. اظهرت الدراسة ان التفشي المصلي ل (GADA و IA-2A) كان بنسبة ٨٨.٦% و ٤٠% على التوالي في مرضى داء السكري النوع الاول. كان عدد مرضى داء السكري النوع الاول واقرباء الدرجة الاولى الذين كان المستوى الاعلى من الطبيعي ل (C-peptide) منخفضاً لديهم اكثر مما كان ذلك المستوى مرتفناً لديهم وكذلك الحال بالنسبة للمستوى الطبيعي لمعلم (TAC) لدى مرضى السكري النوع الاول، وهذا ينطبق ايضاً على المعدل المعياري لهذين المعلمين. فيما يتعلق بمستوى تعبير (miRNAs)، كانت تكرارات المستوى المرتفع و/او المعدل المعياري ل (miRNA-25) منخفضان بشكل ملحوظ لدى مرضى داء السكري النوع الاول واقرباء الدرجة الاولى وبحساسية تشخيصية للسكري قدرها ٩٤.٧% وبخصوصية ١٠٠%. اظهرت نتائج الدراسة بان مستوى (miRNA-375) كان منخفضاً بنسبة ٣٥% لدى مرضى السكري النوع الاول وبنسبة ١٠% لدى اقرباء الدرجة الاولى، بينما كان المعدل المعياري لهذا المعلم اعلى معنوياً بين افراد اقرباء الدرجة الاولى مقارنة بالافراد الاصحاء ظاهرياً. لم يكن هنالك فرقاً ملحوظاً في ايجابية (IA-2A) ومستويات (C-peptide) و (miRNA-375) عند اجراء المقارنة بين افراد (GADA⁺) و (GADA⁻)، بينما كان مستوى (miRNA-25) اقل معنوياً بين افراد (GADA⁺) مقارنة بافراد (GADA⁻) لمجموعتي داء السكري النوع الاول واقرباء الدرجة الاولى وكان مستوى (GADA) يرتبط ايجاباً بزيادة تعبير (miRNA-25) لمرضى داء السكري النوع الاول ومن جانب اخر كان مستوى (GADA) قد ارتبط سلبياً مع مستوى (TAC) في مرضى داء السكري النوع الاول وكان هذا الارتباط غائباً بين ايجابية (IA-2A) والمستوى المصلي ل (TAC) وهذا يعني المشاركة الحيوية ل (GADA) في الاجهاد التاكسدي البنكرياسي. كان الفرق ملحوظاً في مستويات (C-peptide و miRNA-25) بين افراد (IA-2A⁺) و (IA-2A⁻) حيث كان منخفضاً في افراد

(IA-2A⁺) من افراد (IA-2A⁻)، بينما كان مستوى (miRNA-375) بين افراد اقرباء الدرجة الاولى اعلى معنوياً لدى (IA-2A⁺) مقارنة ب (IA-2A⁻). اضافةً الى ذلك لم يكن لمعلم (TAC) اثراً ملحوظاً على ايجابية (IA-2A) وتركيز (C-peptide). كان مستوى (miRNA-) (25) اقل معنوياً عند الاشخاص الذين لديهم مستوى (C-peptide) اقل من الطبيعي مقارنةً بالاشخاص ذو المستوى الطبيعي او الاعلى من الطبيعي ل (C-peptide)، بينما كان هناك ارتفاعاً ملحوظاً بمستوى (miRNA-375) في الافراد الذين لديهم مستوى (C-peptide) اقل من الطبيعي مقارنةً بالافراد ذو المستوى الطبيعي او الاعلى من الطبيعي ل (C-peptide). علاوة على ذلك، كان مستوى (miRNA-25) اعلى احصائياً عند الافراد الذين يعانون من انخفاض مستوى (miRNA-375) مقارنة باولئك الذين لديهم مستوى مرتفع. واخيراً، مرضى داء السكري النوع الاول واقرباء الدرجة الاولى الذين يعانون من انخفاض مستوى (TAC) الذي يتزامن مع ارتفاع معنوي لمستوى تعبير (miRNA-25) وانخفاض معنوي لمستوى تعبير (miRNA-375). الاستنتاجات الخاصة بهذه الدراسة تدل على ان الجمع بين (GADA و IA-2A و C-peptide) تعتبر طريقة تشخيص فعالة وقليلة التكلفة لمرضى داء السكري النوع الاول والاقرباء من الدرجة الاولى. بالاضافة الى ذلك، وجود (IA-2A) في مصول المرضى والاقرباء من الدرجة الاولى له دوراً كافياً في التنبؤ باجهاد و/او موت خلايا نوع بيتا، بينما (GADA و TAC) ليس لهما اي تأثير على مستوى (C-peptide) وبالتالي لا يمكن الاعتماد عليها كمؤشرات حيوية تنبؤية لاجهاد و/او موت خلايا بيتا. كان مستوى تعبير (miRNA-25) منخفضاً لدى مرضى داء السكري النوع الاول حديثي الاصابة واقرباء الدرجة الاولى، بينما كان مستوى تعبير (miRNA-375) منخفضاً لدى مرضى داء السكري النوع الاول حديثي الاصابة ومرتبعا لدى اقرباء الدرجة الاولى والعلاقة بين وظيفة او كتلة خلايا بيتا المتبقية والمستوى

المصلي ل (miRNA-25) موجبة والتي تدل على الفائدة الممكنة للتعبير المنخفض لهذا المعلم باعتبار علامة حيوية تنبأ باجهااد و/او موت خلايا بيتا. من جهة اخرى، كانت العلاقة بين وظيفة او كتلة خلايا بيتا المتبقية والمستوى المصلي ل (miRNA-375) سالبة والتي تدل على الفائدة الممكنة للتعبير المرتفع لهذا المعلم باعتبار علامة حيوية تنبأ باجهااد و/او موت خلايا بيتا.

الجامعة التقنية الوسطى
كلية التقنيات الصحية والطبية/بغداد

قرار لجنة المناقشة

نحن أعضاء لجنة المناقشة نشهد بأننا قد اطلعنا على اطروحة الطالب الموسومة (التحري على المعلمات الحيوية المحتملة لاجهاد و/او موت خلايا بيتا لدى مرضى السكري النوع الأول في محافظة ذي قار) وناقشنا الطالب (حسن عبد علي خضير) في محتوياتها وفيما له علاقة بها وفي ضوء ذلك وجد بأنه جدير بنيل درجة الدكتوراة التقني في فلسفة تقنيات التحليلات المرضية.

التوقيع:

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الجامعة التقنية الوسطى
كلية التقنيات الصحية و الطبية / بغداد

م / إقرار الخبير الاحصائي

أني الاستاذ المساعد (د. نشأت جاسم محمد) الخبير الاحصائي لأطروحة طالب
الدكتوراة التقني (حسن عبد علي خضير) الموسومة (التحري على المعلومات الخيوية المحتملة
لاجهاد و/او موت خلايا بيتا لدى مرضى السكري النوع الأول في محافظة ذي قار). أقر وأؤيد
سلامتها من الناحية الاحصائية وصلاحيتها للمناقشه وذلك لاستيفائها جميع متطلبات هذا
الجانب.

التوقيع:

الاسم: د. نشأت جاسم محمد

المرتبه العلميه: استاذ مساعد

مكان العمل: الكلية التقنية الادارية/بغداد

التاريخ: 2020 / 1 / 15

الجامعة التقنية الوسطى
كلية التقنيات الصحية والطبية/بغداد

م/إقرار المشرف

اني الأستاذ المساعد (د. مضاء محمد شيت صالح) المشرف على اطروحة طالب الدكتوراة التقني (حسن عبد علي خضير) بموجب الأمر الإداري المرقم (٣١٠٨/٣) والمؤرخ في (٢٠١٨/٥/٨)، قد اطلعت على اطروحة الطالب المذكور والتي أنجزت تحت إشرافي، اقر وأؤيد صلاحيتها للمناقشة لاستيفائها كافة المتطلبات العلمية لدرجة الدكتوراة التقني.

التوقيع:

المشرف: د. مضاء محمد شيت صالح

المرتبة العلمية: أستاذ مساعد

التاريخ: ٢٠٢٠/ ١ / ١٥

م/إقرار المقوم اللغوي

إني (د.م.د. رعد حسن حسين) المقوم اللغوي لاطروحة طالب الدكتوراة التقني (حسن عبد علي خضير) الموسومة (التحري على المعلمات الحيوية المحتملة لاجهاد و/او موت خلايا بيتا لدى مرضى السكري النوع الأول في محافظة ذي قار)، اقر وأؤيد سلامتها اللغوية وصلاحيتها للمناقشة لاستيفائها كافة متطلبات هذا الجانب.

التوقيع:

المقوم اللغوي: د. رعد حسن حسين

المرتبة العلمية: استاذ مساعد

التاريخ: ٢٠٢٠/ ١ / ١٥

م/مصادقة

إني رئيس قسم تقنيات المختبرات الطبية في كلية التقنيات الصحية والطبية/بغداد، أصادق على إقرار المشرف على اطروحة طالب الدكتوراة التقني (حسن عبد علي خضير) وعلى إقرار المقوم اللغوي، واعتبر الاطروحة سالحة للمناقشة من قبل اللجنة الممتحنة المشكلة لهذا الغرض.

التوقيع:

د. صلاح مهدي حسن

المرتبة العلمية: مدرس

رئيس قسم تقنيات المختبرات الطبية

التاريخ: ٢٠٢٠/ ١ / ١٥

بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم

جمهورية العراق
وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
الجامعة التقنية الوسطى
كلية التقنيات الصحية والطبية/بغداد

التحري على المعلمات الحيوية المحتملة لاجهاد و/او موت خلايا بيتا لدى مرضى السكري النوع الأول في محافظة ذي قار

اطروحة مقدمة إلى
مجلس كلية التقنيات الصحية والطبية/بغداد وهي كجزء من متطلبات نيل درجة
الدكتوراة التقني في فلسفة تقنيات التحليلات المرضية

من قبل

حسن عبد علي خضير

بكالوريوس تحليلات مرضية (٢٠١١)
ماجستير تقنيات التحليلات المرضية (٢٠١٤)

بأشراف

د.مضاء محمد شيت صالح
أستاذ مساعد

ربيع الثاني/١٤٤١ هـ

كانون الأول/٢٠١٩ م